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Final report on the political, social and industrial opportunities arising from the use of emerging technologies

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document is the final version of the deliverable “Report on the political, social and industrial opportunities arising from the use of emerging technologies” of the COSMIC Support Action. The purpose is to look into the political, social and industrial implications of the use of emerging technologies in crisis situations, in relation to existing policies and standards for the development and use of such technologies, as well as to highlight the opportunities which may arise for industrial stakeholders and the general public. We also address the inherent challenges and limitations posed by privacy and security issues, in the context of mass utilisation of emerging technologies and information gathering/sharing.

On the policy front, we present applicable measures and current EU legislation such as the Directive on data protection and the “Telecommunications Package”. Proposed reforms in existing legislation in areas such as data protection and the role of the Universal Provider in telecommunication services are presented from the point of view of their effects on crisis-laden social networks services. In a similar fashion, we examine EU policy directions on emerging issues such as the openness of the Internet and the freedom of citizens to access and run applications and content.

With regard to standardisation we identify challenges such as the underlying telecommunications technologies, the presentation layer of social media, the data involved and the means of interacting with social media services. For the latter, we draw attention to the complex interplay between market leaders and their competitors and correspondingly between proprietary and open standards. We also present examples of the standardisation effort at two different international organisations, with differing missions. These are the United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) and the World Wide Web Consortium, otherwise known as W3C. The former is a crisis response organisation, while the latter is a standardisation organisation organised as a community. Their common point, with regard to social networks is that they both, through the need to serve their purpose, recognise the necessity for standardisation in social media and work actively towards its achievement.

Moving on to the subject of privacy and security, we identify and discuss the various privacy-related issues for stakeholders to consider, including the right and expectation to privacy, adequate protection of individuals’ data, adhering to the EU data protection law, informed consent, transparency, proportionality and legitimate purpose, anonymity and the increasing nature of surveillance, including dataveillance, counter-surveillance and lateral surveillance. In addition, we consider the various challenges surrounding the protection of information as well as the potential impact of the use of new media technologies on citizens’ safety. Our findings point to the need for added measures by organisations (and possibly members of the public) with the aim to protect those with whom they are interacting.

Use of social media by the crowds is increasingly becoming ubiquitous. Proliferation and integration of social media, most specifically social network sites and micro-blogging into the daily routines of individuals have allowed people to link and interact with each other without being limited by time and spatial constraints. This increased connectivity enabled by social media may provide opportunities for social activism. We reviewed secondary data regarding recent social movements to outline how social media facilitate mobilisation and transnational communication as well as potentially changing how activist networks organise.

Throughout chapter three, authors have also provided a series of recommendations on potential measures that can be taken in order to help promote better awareness and response to these challenges, thereby enabling greater opportunities to be gained from the use of social media in crisis management.

DRAFT

1 INTRODUCTION

Understanding the contribution of social media and other (relevant) new media applications in crisis management requires an examination of the political, social and industrial considerations of existing and emerging technologies, including social networking sites such as Facebook and Twitter for crisis management. By doing so, partners will explore political, social and industrial opportunities and challenges concerning the use of existing and emerging new media applications in crisis management activities. The findings of this work will go some way towards populating our recommendations and guidelines in workpackage 6.

The present deliverable, a preliminary report, D3.2.2 “Final report on the political, social and industrial opportunities from the use of emerging technologies” contains four chapters. In addition to the introduction, chapter 2, explores existing policies, standards and opportunities relating to the use of emerging technologies in crisis situations. Partners will focus their efforts on identifying existing policies and standards for the development and use of social media oriented technologies as well as on examining any opportunities that may arise for industrial stakeholders and the public. Specifically, partners will explore legislation around data protection, telecommunications and other (relevant) upcoming EU developments such as updates of existing Directives and policy directions contained in the Digital Agenda.

In addition, technological challenges such as telecommunications technologies, the presentation layer of social media, the data involved, and the means of interacting with social media services will be examined. Attention will be paid to the complex interplay between market leaders and their competitors and correspondingly between proprietary and open standards.

Chapter 3 of this report will examine the challenges associated with privacy and security when utilising new media applications, particularly social media, as part of crisis management activities. Such challenges include: awareness of and appropriate consideration of EU policies on privacy and data protection, the need for transparency in operations, data protection considerations, the ability to maintain the anonymity of individuals during the sharing of data and the secondary use of data. Partners will also consider the growing impact of surveillance related challenges and opportunities, including: dataveillance, counter-surveillance and lateral surveillance. The chapters’ investigation into security issues include: protection of information from loss or theft, reliability and accuracy of information and vigilante justice.

The increased ability to interact with social network and micro-blogging sites has also enabled opportunities for social activism. Using secondary data regarding recent social movements, the way social media facilitate mobilisation and transnational communication resulting into new activist networks will also be explored.

The report concludes in Chapter 4, where partners summarise the most important findings concerning the role of social media in crisis management, in areas such as applicable legislation in the EU, policy directions, the standards landscape and the privacy, security and activism related challenges arising.

2 EXISTING POLICIES, STANDARDS AND OPPORTUNITIES

The chapter will examine the political, social and industrial implications of the use of emerging technologies for crisis situations. At this first stage, partners will focus on the identification of existing policies and standards for the development and use of such technologies as well as the opportunities which may arise for policy makers, industrial stakeholders and the general public. The first part of this chapter provides an overview of policies which at European level affect social media, followed by a discussion on the role of standardisation and its use in relevant emerging technologies.

2.1 POLICIES AT EUROPEAN LEVEL

We examine the policy framework at the European level with regards to issues akin to social media, such as the protection of personal data, the provision of bandwidth for the operation of social media sites, Internet openness and neutrality, and interoperability.

2.1.1 Personal data

Although the privacy of citizens must be respected and protected by law, this must not become a hindrance to the free movement of voluntarily supplied personal data, which is an essential element of social networks.

As presented in the Europa website¹, Directive 95/46/EC² is the reference text, at European level, on the protection of personal data. The Directive comprises of a regulatory framework to balance the protection of privacy for individuals against free movement of personal data within the European Union (EU). The main features include strict limitations on the collection and use of personal data and the obligation of Member States to establish an overseeing body operating independently at the national level.

Although the Directive concerns data processed by automated and manual means, its application does not include activities not covered by the Community Law (such as public security, defence or state security) and the processing of data by individuals (called “natural persons” in the Directive) for purely personal or household activities.

The Directive outlines guidelines with respect to the processing of personal data by taking into account factors such as:

- the **quality** of the data, which must be accurate, up to date, lawfully and fairly processed and collected
- the **legitimacy** of the processing, and the consent of the data subject
- the exclusion of special **categories** of processing, such as information regarding racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, beliefs, medical data and others
- the **information** given to the data subject, such as for example the identity of the data processor, his purpose etc.
- the data subject's **right of access** to data kept relating to him/her
- **exemptions and restrictions**: on matters such as national security, defence, public security, prosecution of criminal offences and others

¹ http://europa.eu/legislation_summaries/information_society/data_protection/114012_en.htm

² EUR-Lex, access to European Union law,

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX:31995L0046:EN:NOT>

- the **right to object** to the processing of data
- the **confidentiality** and security of processing
- the **notification** of processing to a supervisory authority

The data protection Directive (including amending Acts such as Regulation (EC) No 1882/2003³) is currently undergoing an update process. As described in the dedicated Commission’s mini-site⁴, advances in the Internet and the way the personal data landscape has changed since the adoption of the Directive (1995), via technologies such as eCommerce, social networks, online games and cloud computing, have highlighted the need for strengthening protection of personal online data. Key changes proposed by the Commission are:

1. Guaranteeing easy access to one’s own data and the freedom to transfer personal data from one service provider to another.
2. Establishing the **right to be forgotten** to help people better manage data protection risks online. When individuals no longer want their data to be processed and there are no legitimate grounds for retaining it, the data will be deleted.
3. Ensuring that whenever the consent of the individual is required for the processing of their personal data, it is always given explicitly
4. Ensuring a single set of rules applicable across the EU.
5. Clear rules on when EU law applies to data controllers outside the EU

The new proposals are currently under debate by the Council and the European Parliament. We draw attention to proposal two, due to its significance to social networks. As data exchanged via these networks grows larger and larger, so does information related to each member of such a network. Given that the most popular of these networks (such as Twitter, Facebook and others) have evolved into private companies, the amount of personal data held by them can be disproportionately large. The example of the Austrian student who requested the information held on him by Facebook, quoted in the Commission’s factsheet⁵, is illuminating: 1224 pages were sent to the requestor, much of which he himself had deleted. The “right to be forgotten” or the “right to oblivion”, as it is also called, contained in Article 17 of the proposed legislation⁶, serves this purpose. The Eurobarometer 359 findings (June 2011) quoted in the same factsheet show that only 26% of social network users and even fewer online shoppers (18%) feel in complete control of their data.

One should note that not every country or stakeholder concerned agrees with the proposed article 17. Among them is the UK, whose Ministry of Justice is of the opinion that the very phrase “right to be forgotten”, as proposed by the European Commission, “raises unrealistic and unfair expectations of the proposals” and poses “potentially impossible requirements for data controllers to manage third-party erasure”.⁷ Similar fears about the effectiveness of

³ EUR-Lex, access to European Union law, “Regulation (EC) No 1882/2003 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 September 2003”,

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX:32003R1882:EN:NOT>

⁴ <http://ec.europa.eu/justice/data-protection/minisite/>

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ EUR-Lex, access to European Union law, “Proposal for a DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL”, COM/2012/010 final - 2012/0010 (COD),

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX:52012PC0010:en:NOT>

⁷ The Guardian, “Britain seeks opt-out of new European social media privacy laws”, 4th April 2013, <http://www.theguardian.com/technology/2013/apr/04/britain-opt-out-right-to-be-forgotten-law>

Article 17 have been expressed by other organisations⁸ such as the London-based group “Privacy International” and Facebook themselves, especially when personal data have been spread to third parties prior to the exercise of the right to oblivion.

Finally, the issue of privacy in electronic communications is further treated at the EU level via the 2002 [Privacy and Electronic Communications](#) Directive⁹ of the Telecommunications Package (treated in the next section). The Directive poses additional safeguards on the processing of personal data subject to communications services in areas such as:¹⁰

- **Processing security** by the communications service provider
- **Confidentiality of communications** which asks Member States to ensure the confidentiality of communications over a public network via legislation
- **Data retention** which poses erasure and anonymisation of data no longer required for the purpose of a communication or billing, with, however, exceptions regarding criminal investigations or national security, defence and public security matters.
- **Unsolicited communications (spamming)**
- **Cookies**
- **Public directories** listing only after consent is given
- **Controls** consisting of a system of legal sanctions for infringements and the establishment of National Regulatory Authorities (NRA).

An in-depth discussion of the privacy-related challenges relevant to the use of social media in emergency situations is included in Chapter 3 of this document.

2.1.2 Telecommunications

European policy on telecommunications relies on the so-called “Telecommunications Package”¹¹, a set of Directives, Decisions and Regulations aimed at the opening-up of the relevant market to competition in relation to technological developments and the need for stimulating investment.

The main Directive (Framework Directive) is 2002/21/EC¹² plus four other Directives, namely the “Authorisation Directive”¹³, the “Access Directive”¹⁴, the “Universal Service Directive”¹⁵ and the “Privacy and Electronic Communications Directive”¹⁶, all dated in 2002.

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ Europa, summaries of EU legislation, “Data protection in the electronic communications sector”
http://europa.eu/legislation_summaries/information_society/legislative_framework/124120_en.htm

¹⁰ Ibid.

¹¹ Europa, summaries of EU legislation, “Regulatory framework for electronic communications”,
http://europa.eu/legislation_summaries/information_society/legislative_framework/124216a_en.htm

¹² EUR-Lex, access to European Union law, “Directive 2002/21/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 7 March 2002”,

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX:32002L0021:EN:NOT>

¹³ Europa, summaries of EU legislation, “Authorisation of electronic communications networks and services”,
http://europa.eu/legislation_summaries/information_society/legislative_framework/124164_en.htm

¹⁴ Europa, summaries of EU legislation, “Access to electronic communications networks”,
http://europa.eu/legislation_summaries/information_society/legislative_framework/124108i_en.htm

¹⁵ Europa, summaries of EU legislation, “Universal service and users' rights”,
http://europa.eu/legislation_summaries/information_society/legislative_framework/124108h_en.htm

¹⁶ Europa, summaries of EU legislation, “Data protection in the electronic communications sector”,
http://europa.eu/legislation_summaries/information_society/legislative_framework/124120_en.htm

This is supplemented by the “Radio Spectrum Decision”¹⁷, the 2009 amendments via the “Better law-making”¹⁸ and the “Citizens’ rights”¹⁹ Directives and the Body of European regulators for Electronic Communications²⁰ (BEREC).

The implications of the telecoms legislation at the European level to social networks lie on their provisions on privacy and on the Internet as a communications medium. As examined in the previous section, in what follows we elaborate on the latter issue. Historically, there were no provisions included in the basic legislative body of the 2002 (Telecoms Package) as regards to the features of an Internet service based on broadband. The important concept of the Universal Service Obligation (USO) included in Article 15 of the 2002 Access Directive (2002/22/EC) appears to have been superseded. Not only does it not apply to mobile communications, but it also does not cover broadband Internet services. A Communication from the Commission²¹ in 2008 posed the question of whether the USO “is an appropriate tool to advance broadband development and mobile telephony or whether these services should be left to other Community instruments or to national measures.”²² The debate has yet to be settled at EU level. The 2009 Citizens’ Rights Directive (ref. Ibid.), among others, states that:

- “...Data connections to the public communications network at a fixed location should be capable of supporting data communications at rates sufficient for access to online services such as those provided via the public Internet...” and that
- “...it is not appropriate to mandate a specific data or bit rate at Community level. Flexibility is required to allow Member States to take measures, where necessary, to ensure that a data connection is capable of supporting satisfactory data rates which are sufficient to permit functional Internet access...”

This constitutes a deviation from the 2002 Universal Service directive, where a limit of 56kbps was explicitly set for a narrowband connection, in favour of shifting the burden to the Member States. Although more flexibility is there, the availability of a minimum bandwidth under all conditions (to cater for periods of stresses caused by crises) is essential if social media are to function as security enhancers for citizens under duress. As COSMIC has already demonstrated²³, the role of social media in crises has, in many cases, been helpful in

¹⁷ Europa, summaries of EU legislation, “Regulatory framework for radio spectrum policy”, http://europa.eu/legislation_summaries/information_society/radiofrequencies/124218a_en.htm

¹⁸ EUR-Lex, access to European Union law, “Directive 2009/140/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 November 2009”, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX:32009L0140:EN:NOT>

¹⁹ EUR-Lex, access to European Union law, “Directive 2009/136/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 November 2009”, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX:32009L0136:EN:NOT>

²⁰ Europa, summaries of EU legislation, “The Body of European Regulators for Electronic Communications (BEREC)”, http://europa.eu/legislation_summaries/information_society/legislative_framework/si0015_en.htm

²¹ Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on the second periodic review of the scope of universal service in electronic communications networks and services in accordance with Article 15 of Directive 2002/22/EC (COM (2008) 572 final), <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX:52008DC0572:EN:NOT>

²² http://europa.eu/legislation_summaries/information_society/legislative_framework/124108h_en.htm

²³ Papadimitriou, A., Yannopoulos, A., Kotsiopoulos, I., Finn, R., Watson, H, Wadhwa, K and Baruh, L., “Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations”, *Deliverable 2.2 of the COSMIC project*, 30 September 2013.

saving lives. From that point of view, one can argue that a minimum guaranteed bandwidth able to support social networking and other web 2.0 functions throughout the EU, sustainable under adverse conditions (such as those of a crisis), would be desirable.

Policy issue

The lack of an EU-wide imposed minimum bandwidth can have implications on the overall true ability of an internet connection supplied by a Universal Provider to support social network based communication, especially during a crisis.

To serve the general debate and to prepare the road for future amendments, a range of policy options on the general issue of extending a USO to broadband services can be found at a report submitted to the Commission in October 2010.²⁴

2.1.3 Towards 2020: the Digital Agenda

Given the previous section, one should not infer that there is no long term policy direction for broadband Internet in Europe. The debate, as shown above, centres on how this can be conducted in a more efficient way. Pillar IV of the Digital Agenda for Europe on “Fast and Ultra-fast Internet Access”²⁵ states that “to match world leaders like South Korea and Japan, Europe needs download rates of 30 Mbps for all of its citizens and at least 50% of European households subscribing to internet connections above 100 Mbps by 2020.” More revealing of the policy intentions is Action 42²⁶ of the Pillar IV, where the role of public intervention in the deployment of broadband networks is considered crucial in counteracting the “risk that the deployment of fast broadband networks will focus mainly in a few high-density zones leaving rural and remote areas excluded.”

Although policy at technical (bandwidth availability) level is important, preservation of the openness of the Internet and of the freedom of citizens to access and run applications and content are becoming increasingly relevant. In fact, this is a consequence of the growth of traffic via the Internet, which has resulted in non-transparent traffic management techniques used by Internet Service Providers (ISPs) and which, in turn, result in Peer-to-Peer (P2P) and VoIP restrictions in fixed and mobile networks. Recognising this threat, Action 115²⁷ of Pillar IV (Recommendation on safeguarding the open Internet for consumers) calls for EU action to “promote a common regulatory approach among National Regulatory Authorities (NRAs) towards the open Internet and provide a clear and predictable framework for all stakeholders in Europe.” Although this does not appear today as a direct threat to social networking (as envisaged in its use during emergencies), use of increased bandwidth for potentially life saving video-streaming activities, for example, may be adversely affected when needed (i.e. during crisis) by traffic management policies of the ISP.

Partial application of the envisaged regulatory framework on the open Internet is also included in the 2009 telecoms Directives (see previous section), according to which

²⁴ Van Dijk Management Consultants, SVP Advisors, time.lex, “Final Report for the study on the Impact of EU Policy options for revision of the universal service provision”, Assignment under the Framework Contract for Impact Assessment and Evaluation-Related-Services N° 2007/035 – LOT 2, 25 October 2010

²⁵ <http://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/our-goals/pillar-iv-fast-and-ultra-fast-internet-access>

²⁶ <http://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/pillar-iv-fast-and-ultra-fast-internet-access/action-42-adopt-eu-broadband-communication>

²⁷ <http://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/pillar-iv-fast-and-ultra-fast-internet-access/action-115-recommendation-safeguarding-open-internet>

subscribers should be able to access and distribute information or run applications and services of their choice, under transparency and suitable quality of service (QoS) levels across Europe. National Regulatory Authorities (NRAs) are also empowered to safeguard net neutrality.

2.1.4 Other considerations

Social networks, by nature, offer services (not a priori defined) which share arbitrary, unstructured information with specific, selected groups of people. Their main mechanism is forms of authentication, designed to restrict access to previously defined groups. One can legitimately claim that in times of crises wider access of the information any such network contains by, for example, other such networks and possibly emergency services is important, thus the need for interoperability protocols. The difficulties should not be underestimated, however, as personal data leaks can have serious consequences: residence addresses made widely known can result in assaults and burglaries and personal life events can become the object of malicious exploitation. Such cases have been extensively treated under the deliverables of WP4 of COSMIC.²⁸

Policy issue

The tradeoffs between privacy and the need for open interoperability standards (at technical and semantic level) for social network data, especially in the case of an emergency, are a challenging issue for technical (protocol design) as well as policy research. This is in view of the trade-off required between wider access to information and the resulting increased risk of malicious exploitation of personal data.

2.2 STANDARDISATION AND SOCIAL MEDIA

This chapter focuses on the technical state of the art in standards that apply to social media, from a crisis management perspective. The evolution of social media is influenced by many, strong and potentially contradictory forces, such as market forces, the common interest, government regulation, and unpredictable scientific and technological innovation. Social media are a relatively new technology, and are still evolving rapidly, thus it is important to consider already-existing standards, gaps where standardisation is missing, as well as current trends with respect to standardisation. In the context of social media the question of standardisation is a complicated and important one, therefore in the present chapter we focus on this topic, since social media are the core concern of the COSMIC project.

2.2.1 Discussion of standardisation of social media in the context of crisis management

The value of standardisation for practical technology is significant across a number of dimensions, including the following^{29, 30}:

- Compatibility

²⁸ Lemi Baruh, Hayley Watson, Kim Hagen, Kush Wadhwa, Zeynep Günel, Haluk Mert Bal, Salvatore Scifo, Yusuf Salman, “Final report on citizen involvement and ethics”, COSMIC Deliverable D4.2.2, Chapter 3, October 2014

²⁹ Langenberg, T. (2005). “*Standardisation and Expectations.*” Berlin: Springer-Verlag.

³⁰ Murphy, C. N.; Yates, J. (2008). “*The International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) : Global Governance Through Voluntary Consensus.*” New York: Routledge.

- definition³¹: *“in telecommunications, compatibility is the capability of two or more items or components of equipment or material to exist or function in the same system or environment without mutual interference; in computing, compatibility is the capability that allows the substitution of one subsystem (storage facility), or of one functional unit (e.g., hardware, software), for the originally designated system or functional unit in a relatively transparent manner, without loss of information and without the introduction of errors.”*
- Interoperability
 - definition³²: *“interoperability is the ability of making systems and organizations to work together (inter-operate). While the term was initially defined for information technology or systems engineering services to allow for information exchange, a more broad definition takes into account social, political, and organizational factors that impact system to system performance.”*
- Commoditisation
 - definition³³: *“commoditisation is defined as the process by which goods that have economic value and are distinguishable in terms of attributes (uniqueness or brand) end up becoming simple commodities in the eyes of the market or consumers. It is the movement of a market from differentiated to undifferentiated price competition and from monopolistic to perfect competition.”*
- Safety
 - definition³⁴: *“safety is the state of being "safe", the condition of being protected against physical, social, spiritual, financial, political, emotional, occupational, psychological, educational or other types or consequences of failure, damage, error, accidents, harm or any other event which could be considered non-desirable. Safety can also be defined to be the control of recognised hazards to achieve an acceptable level of risk. This can take the form of being protected from the event or from exposure to something that causes health or economical losses. It can include protection of people or of possessions.”*
- Quality
 - definition³⁵: *“quality in business, engineering and manufacturing has a pragmatic interpretation as the non-inferiority or superiority of something; it is also defined as fitness for purpose. Quality is a perceptual, conditional, and somewhat subjective attribute and may be understood differently by different people. Consumers may focus on the specification quality of a product/service, or how it compares to competitors in the marketplace. Producers might measure the conformance quality, or degree to which the product/service was produced correctly. Support personnel may measure quality in the degree that a product is reliable, maintainable, or sustainable. Simply put, a quality item (an item that has quality) has the ability to perform satisfactorily in service and is suitable for its intended purpose.”*
- Repeatability

³¹ <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Compatibility>

³² <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Interoperability>

³³ <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Commoditization>

³⁴ <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Safety>

³⁵ <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quality> (business)

- definition³⁶: *“repeatability or test-retest reliability is the variation in measurements taken by a single person or instrument on the same item and under the same conditions. A less-than-perfect test-retest reliability causes test-retest variability. Such variability can be caused by, for example, intra-individual variability and intra-observer variability. A measurement may be said to be repeatable when this variation is smaller than some agreed limit. Test-retest variability is practically used, for example, in medical monitoring of conditions. In these situations, there is often a predetermined "critical difference", and for differences in monitored values that are smaller than this critical difference, the possibility of pre-test variability as a sole cause of the difference may be considered in addition to, for examples, changes in diseases or treatments.”*

Standardisation can be seen by both industry and consumers as offering a trade-off comprising significant advantages as well as significant disadvantages.

- For industry
 - Standardisation is capable of infusing life into a market, helping it to grow. This occurs because standardisation facilitates different companies to bring skills and ideas to the market, improving their internal efficiency and especially the collaboration between companies addressing the same market, and ultimately leading to their better performance and results. Therefore, industry that profits due to the existence of the market should view standardisation as a great opportunity to increase profit.
 - Standardisation is a process of “levelling the playing field” and increasing competition. This is because it lowers the barrier of entry into the market, and allows specialists to contribute to the market, thus breaking an initial monopoly or oligopoly that may have developed under the control of early dominant companies. Therefore, industry that is already in full control of a market, or aiming to gain such control, can view standardisation as a great threat against its opportunity for monopolistic profits.
- For consumers
 - Standardisation supports the development of higher-quality and less-expensive products and services. This occurs because of the efficiency gains and the exploitation of specialist contributions as discussed above. Therefore, consumers should view standardisation as a great opportunity to motivate industry to fairly serve the true needs of the consumers.
 - Standardisation inhibits innovation when it decreases the potential returns that industry expects from developing new and improved products and services. This occurs because companies forced to offer standard products or services cannot innovate so as to differentiate their offerings, adding value for the customer and competing effectively with their competitors – price differentiation becomes the dominant point of competition. Therefore, consumers can view standardisation as a mechanism that suppresses quality in the products and services available to them.

³⁶ <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Repeatability>

Social media are innovative services, based on state-of-the-art technologies, and are constantly evolving. We can use a distinction applied to the question of standardisation of Cloud Computing by Krechmer³⁷ to elucidate the social media standardisation question:

- *Standardisation of similarity* is the process of controlling a market so as to enforce similarities between the products and services themselves. Although the benefits described above do apply in this case, standardisation of similarity forces the homogeneity of the products and services, thus reducing variation in the market, and thereby reducing innovation. Standardisation of similarity is appropriate for mature markets and technologies, and for dimensions of the products and services where homogeneity is more important than innovation – for example, minimum food quality or the matching characteristics of roads and automobiles.
- *Standardisation of compatibility* is the process of controlling a market so as to enforce different products and services in the market to be usable in conjunction – for example, the Universal Serial Bus allows any computer to be connected to any peripheral device, and it should be noted that the connection technology itself (ports, connectors, wires, controllers) is not a core product in the computing market, but it *is* a core enabler for other products of greater direct value.

It is easy to see that standardisation of similarity in the context of social media is a preposterous idea. It would imply social networking sites being constrained to offer similar services. For example, a Facebook post comprising more than 140 characters is too long to be tweeted on Twitter, so an effort towards standardisation of similarity might call for all posts to be short enough so that they can be shared by users regardless of which Social Networking Site they use to transmit the message. This is clearly an (utterly) undesirable scenario. However, the irrelevance of standardisation of similarity to social media does not imply irrelevance of standardisation in general to social media. Standardisation of compatibility is relevant, practically feasible and capable of generating great value for social media users.

Standardisation of compatibility in the context of social media means that social media as well as other tools, such as data mining tools or content archiving tools, are able to access and use the functions and content of all (other) social media. Very good examples of this capability arise in the context of crisis management:

- Data mining tools accessing tweets transmitted from a disaster area, in order to accurately assess the situation on the ground, e.g. predicting an outbreak of a disease.
- Crisis mapping tools drawing images posted to a photo sharing network from a disaster area, in order to enable the visualisation of the geographic aspects of the disaster, e.g. where the damage is the worst.
- Content aggregation tools, enabling a humanitarian agency to monitor calls for help that are transmitted through any variety of social media.

Standardisation of compatibility can be pursued using the technique of *adaptability standards*, which are *meta standards*³⁸ enforcing compatibility throughout the evolving lifecycles of the addressed technologies, by explicitly modelling and managing a technology's

- capabilities,
- their versioning,

³⁷ Ken Krechmer, "Cloud computing standardization," in *How does electrotechnology impact economic, social and environmental development? Winning papers from the IEC-IEEE Challenge 2012*, p. 15-25, Geneva, Switzerland.

³⁸ K. Krechmer, "Fundamental Nature of Standards", Technical Perspective, *IEEE Communications Magazine*, Vol. 38, #6, June, 2000, p. 70. Adaptability standards are termed etiquettes in this paper.

- a negotiation process between components that allows compatible interfaces to be determined whenever required, and
- the relevant intellectual property rights

While it is acceptable that for-profit companies avoid standardisation of similarity, which would act indefensibly against their interests, the avoidance or boycotting of *adaptability standards* hurts the overall market and aims to lock potential competitors out of that market altogether, therefore it can be morally rejected as a business practice. When companies pursue such a strategy, the result is often a “standards war”, more usually termed a “formats war”,³⁹ where competitors each aim to force de facto standards upon the market by achieving their own format’s popular adoption, giving the winner power over the market.

Following this discussion, the remainder of this chapter addresses the key areas where standardisation of compatibility can increase the value of social media, especially in the context of crisis management. Since standardisation of similarity is inappropriate, and also not evidenced in the market, there is nothing to document here about standardisation of the core services of social media, such as posting, viewing and searching content through a Social Networking Site’s custom user interface. Rather, connectivity and compatibility issues of social media are addressed. Specifically, we consider:

- standardisation of telecommunications technology underlying social media
- standardisation of the delivery and presentation layers of social media
- standardisation of social media data
- standardisation of technical means for interacting with social media services

The first two of these standardisation challenges are, largely, already-solved issues, while the last two of these standardisation challenges are, largely, unsolved issues. It is interesting to consider them together, as this illustrates the gradual progress of social media standardisation.

2.2.2 Standardisation of telecommunications technology underlying social media

Telecommunications have been the subject of standardisation since at least 1865⁴⁰. As discussed in D1.2 of COSMIC, telecommunication technologies are highly mature, highly standardised, and offer a well defined technological layer for data transmission over which social media can be built. Newer telecommunication technologies periodically appear and provide new capabilities, such as mobility, but applications exploiting them can remain agnostic to the technical details of the data transmission process and rely on standardised abstractions of this transmission capability, such as messages, connections etc. In our discussion on policy issues in this document, we also discuss the European regulatory framework for electronic communications⁴¹, which, it should be noted, regulates standards aimed at organising and perpetuating these conditions.

2.2.3 Standardisation of the delivery and presentation layers of social media

Social Media are delivered either as web pages or through mobile apps. Mobile apps primarily target smartphones and exploit the devices’ capabilities to the maximum, whereas delivering social media through mobile web browsers benefits from standardisation; this

³⁹ <http://www.switched.com/2010/09/24/format-wars-a-history-of-what-could-have-been-from-betamax-to>

⁴⁰ <http://www.itu.int/en/history/Pages/Home.aspx>

⁴¹ http://europa.eu/legislation_summaries/information_society/legislative_framework/124216a_en.htm

dilemma, weighing customisation versus standardisation, remains unresolved and the subject of debate⁴², yet in the long term the balance seems to be tipping in favour of standardisation⁴³: HTML5, despite its not yet being finalised, allows major benefits such as “build once, deploy to many” (as opposed to the need to implement a separate app for each platform, such as different mobile operating systems, but also different smart TV solutions, different in-vehicle entertainment systems, etc) and better searchability.

Web standardisation has a long and uneven history^{44,45}, but, ultimately, globally accepted and almost universally implemented, largely consensual, de jure standards have prevailed⁴⁶. Developers can confidently rely on a broad variety of standards for the delivery and presentation⁴⁷ of the social media products on offer, including:

- (X)HTML, CSS, DOM, XForms, SVG, RDF, GRDDL, OWL⁴⁸
- HTML5, Microdata, Web Applications, Web Forms, Web Workers⁴⁹
- Unicode Standard, Unicode Technical Reports (UTRs)⁵⁰
- Web site engineering and other IT standards, for example, user interface standards, PNG functional specification⁵¹
- ECMAScript⁵²
- Domain names, IP address coordination, protocol assignments⁵³
- Internet standard (STD) documents, Request for Comments (RFC) documents, for example, proper use of HTTP, MIME, and URI⁵⁴
- Dublin Core Metadata⁵⁵

2.2.4 Standardisation of social media data

Social media data is intrinsically inter-referenced, since the handling of relationships is the main differentiator between social networking services and the older Web; often, the entities whose relationships are defined in social media data are real-world entities, such as people. Additionally, social media data is vast: billions of users are generating data on a regular basis. Finally, social media data is rich in semantics and in digital media content, encompassing structured and semi-structured representations of a variety of human relationships⁵⁶ as well as digital media content such as images and videos.

⁴² <http://www.theguardian.com/media-network/media-network-blog/2013/feb/07/html5-native-apple-android-strategy>

⁴³ <http://www.wired.com/insights/2013/09/auto-industry-to-rev-up-the-death-of-native-apps-rise-of-html5>

⁴⁴ <http://www.w3.org/Consortium/facts.html#history>

⁴⁵ <http://www.webstandards.org>

⁴⁶ Sikos, Leslie. “*Web standards: mastering HTML5, CSS3, and XML.*” Apress, 2011.

⁴⁷ It should be noted that delivery includes the conceptual structure of the content, which includes the structured markup and the semantic markup of the content – both underlying the final presentation features which determine the visual characteristics of the content

⁴⁸ www.w3.org

⁴⁹ www.whatwg.org

⁵⁰ www.unicode.org

⁵¹ www.iso.org

⁵² www.ecmainternational.org

⁵³ www.iana.org

⁵⁴ www.ietf.org

⁵⁵ www.dublincore.org

⁵⁶ When one user “Likes” another, this is an explicit assertion of a positive response of the first user towards the second. However, if one user tags another in a photograph, this provides implicit evidence that the first user recognises the second visually. There are very many such items of relationship information to be accessed or discovered in social media data.

A useful representation of social media data will effectively deal with these characteristics. It will be able to explicitly identify or define the entities it refers to, and represent the relationships between them. It will be amenable to efficient, automated processing by computers, as no human user is capable of manually examining all the social media data being produced. Finally, it will be compatible with a modelling mechanism capable of capturing the rich semantics of the data.

Linked Data provides a standardised way to represent data, which is highly appropriate to social media data. Linked Data⁵⁷ “refers to data published on the Web in such a way that (i) it is machine-readable, (ii) its meaning is explicitly defined, (iii) it is linked to other external data sets, and (iv) can in turn be linked to from external data sets. Linked Data requires the identification of entities with URI references that can be dereferenced over the HTTP protocol into a common semantic data model, such as RDF. The use of Linked Data is advantageous as it inherently facilitates interoperability and integration of data from disparate data sources. It also opens up possibilities for carrying out inference and analytics over the data.”

Although Linked Data is an excellent representation mechanism for social media data, as a generic framework it is agnostic to the specific semantics of social media data. Therefore, Linked Data standardises a structural representation mechanism that is appropriate for social media data, but not a semantic model of social media data.

2.2.4.1 Semantic models and ontologies

In order to represent the internal semantics of social media data, a semantic model, or at least a descriptive data or object schema, is required. As Ouksel and Sheth⁵⁸ point out, semantics in this case involves “mapping of objects in the model or computational world onto the real world” by taking into account of “the issues that involve human interpretation, or meaning and use of data and information”. Making “machine-sense” of a world of human communications and relations, such as social media, will have to involve merging of data which corresponds to the same (or adequately similar) real-world entity or concept. This implies semantic ambiguities, which, in turn, need to be resolved in a definite and explicit way via metadata and implicit context assumptions.

There are no easy solutions here: semantics and semantic integration or even semantic interoperability are still widely open and actively pursued research areas. As the late Joseph Goguen explained:⁵⁹ “despite some optimistic projections to the contrary, the representation of meaning, in anything like the sense that humans use that term, is far beyond current information technology. As explored in detail in fields such as Computer Supported Cooperative Work (CSCW), understanding the meaning of a document often requires a deep understanding of its social context, including how it was produced, how it is used, its role in organisational politics, its relation to other documents, its relation to other organisations, and much more, depending on the particular situation. Moreover, all these contexts may be changing at a rapid rate, as may the documents themselves, and the context of the data is also

⁵⁷ Bizer, C., “The Emerging Web of Linked Data” *Intelligent Systems*, 24(5), pp.87–92, 2009.

⁵⁸ Ouksel, Aris M. and Sheth, Amit P., Semantic Interoperability in Global Information Systems: A Brief Introduction to the Research Area and the Special Section. *SIGMOD Record*, 28(1):5–12., 1999

⁵⁹ Goguen, J.A., “Information Integration, Databases and Ontologies”, 2006, <http://www.cs.ucsd.edu/~goguen/projs/data.html>

often both indeterminate and evolving. Another complication is that the same document may be used in multiple ways, some of which can be very different from others. These complexities mean that it is unrealistic to expect any single semantics to adequately reflect the meaning of the documents of some class for every purpose.”

Two important constituents of a semantic model today are a vocabulary, i.e. a set of terms consistent across different contexts with a well-defined meaning and an ontology, broadly defined as a set of contextual relationships on a defined vocabulary. The use of the concept of ontology began in the early 90s, primarily as a tool of the Artificial Intelligence community, and has continued to gain popularity with the Semantic Web community and the relevant technologies. Although differences exist among the computer science community, an instructive description was first given by Gruber in 1992, updated in 2009, quoted below.

Ontologies⁶⁰

“In the context of computer and information sciences an ontology defines a set of representational primitives with which to model a domain of knowledge or discourse. The representational primitives are typically classes (or sets), attributes (or properties), and relationships (or relations among class members). The definitions of the representational primitives include information about their meaning and constraints on their logically consistent application. In the context of database systems, ontology can be viewed as a level of abstraction of data models, analogous to hierarchical and relational models, but intended for modelling knowledge about individuals, their attributes, and their relationships to other individuals. Ontologies are typically specified in languages that allow abstraction away from data structures and implementation strategies; in practice, the languages of ontologies are closer in expressive power to first-order logic than languages used to model databases. For this reason, ontologies are said to be at the “semantic” level, whereas database schema are models of data at the “logical” or “physical” level. Due to their independence from lower level data models, ontologies are used for integrating heterogeneous databases, enabling interoperability among disparate systems, and specifying interfaces to independent, knowledge-based services. In the technology stack of the semantic web standards, ontologies are called out as an explicit layer. There are now standard languages and a variety of commercial and open source tools for creating and working with ontologies.”

Ontologies are part of the W3C standards stack for the Semantic Web, used to specify standard conceptual vocabularies for data exchange among systems, query answering services, publication of reusable knowledge bases, and interoperability facilities across multiple, heterogeneous systems and databases. A formal syntax for defining ontologies is OWL, which facilitates greater machine interpretability of web content than that supported by XML, RDF, and RDF Schema (RDF-S) by providing additional vocabulary along with a formal semantics.⁶¹

One word of caution here however: ontologies have been surrounded by disproportionate expectations. Joseph Goguen⁶² warns that correct application and use of such technology necessitates understanding of its limitations. He observes that computer-processable ontologies, which consist of logical axioms that relate terms of interest, have genuine promise

⁶⁰ Gruber, T “Ontology”, *Encyclopedia of Database Systems*, Ling Liu and M. Tamer Özsu (Eds.), Springer-Verlag, 2009., <http://tomgruber.org/writing/ontology-definition-2007.htm>

⁶¹ Web Ontology Language, W3C, OWL Working Group, <http://www.w3.org/TR/owl-features/>

⁶² Goguen, J.A., "Ontology, society and ontotheology", *International Conference on Formal Ontology in Information Systems (FOIS 2004)*, 2004, <https://cseweb.ucsd.edu/~goguen/pps/fois04.pdf>

when restricted to appropriate, well-understood domains. In fact ontologies cannot capture real world semantics but only logical relations between terms. A given domain may also have several ontologies, each in some ways incomplete and/or ambiguous, and possibly written in different ontology languages, based on different logical systems, some of them may not even have a formal semantics.

One of the problems ontologies bring is their growth: *“ontologies unfortunately are proliferating almost as quickly as the datasets that they are meant to describe. Therefore, integrating datasets the semantics of which are given by different ontologies will require that their ontologies be integrated first.”*⁶³ An ontology, formally, is a theory over a logic, i.e. *“logical axioms that relate predicates of interest.”*⁶⁴ To integrate, a rigorous foundation not tied to any specific representational or logical formalism is needed, resulting in approaches with a high level of abstraction, frequently beyond first order logic and model theory.^{65, 66, 67}

The issues above are indicative of the difficulty of the semantic integration problem in the web era. That said, ontology engineering is perhaps the most promising approach currently at our disposal. Standard vocabularies, or formal ontologies representing terms within a domain of knowledge, are already available freely from various organisations on a range of subjects. Examples for general use are:

- The Dublin Core initiative⁶⁸, which creates ontologies for a range of subjects, particularly focusing on common, every day terms and terms important in media.
- OpenCyc⁶⁹, an ontology of everyday, common sense terms, representing the world's largest and most complete general knowledge base and commonsense reasoning engine, which can be user-extended and used as the basis of a wide variety of intelligent applications.

2.2.4.2 Semantic models for social media

A complete semantic model of all social media data would be a very powerful tool, however so far no such model is available. Indeed, any such semantic model would need to be aggressively maintained, since social media themselves, together with their underlying data, are still evolving quite rapidly. Various solutions exist, which partially meet these requirements; these are mainly centred around ontologies which act as specific purpose vocabularies with inter-relationships, some of which are also machine processable. Mainstream examples are as follows:

FOAF (Friend Of A Friend) ontology⁷⁰

⁶³ Goguen, J.A., “Information Integration, Databases and Ontologies”, 2006, <http://www.cs.ucsd.edu/~goguen/projs/data.html>

⁶⁴ Ibid.

⁶⁵ Goguen J., “A Categorical Manifesto”, *Mathematical Structures in Computer Science*, 1 (1991) 49-67

⁶⁶ Goguen J. and Burstall R., “Institutions: Abstract Model Theory for Specification and Programming”, *Journal of the Association for Computing Machinery*, **39**(1) (1992) 95-146

⁶⁷ Barwise J, Seligman J., “Information Flow: Logic of Distributed Systems”. Cambridge 1997, *Tracts in Theoretical Computer Science*, 44

⁶⁸ Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI), <http://dublincore.org>

⁶⁹ OpenCyc ontology, Cycorp, <http://www.opencyc.org>

⁷⁰ <http://www.foaf-project.org>

This is characterised as “an experimental linked information system” and a “computer language defining a dictionary of people-related terms that can be used in structured data”. FOAF’s original idea was to integrate information from a person’s home page with that of his friends, the friends of his friends, etc., i.e. capture relationships that connect people, places and things described on the Web. It uses W3C's RDF (Resource Description Framework) technology, with the ultimate aim to locate documents, people and other entities in the Web based on their properties and inter-relationships; in other words create a Web search system “that's more like a database and less like a lucky dip.”

FOAF initially (early 2000) combined some basic RDF vocabulary plus Dublin Core metadata elements. The vocabulary has grown substantially since then, and continues to evolve by versioning FOAF's terms individually and marking each as ‘stable’, ‘unstable’ or ‘testing’ to help implementors, without causing further versioning problems and vocabulary proliferation. In FOAF people's existence in the virtual world is linked to properties related to online activity or identity, but other concepts, such as family relations, physical address, etc, are not modelled. Similar modelling is provided for organisations or groups with a focus on their existence on the Web (webpage, etc) and this is what makes it particularly suitable for describing such entities on Web-based social platforms.

The easiest way to "get a FOAF file" today is to have a profile on a social Web site that generates it automatically. Other tools such as FOAF-a-matic⁷¹ also exist, as well as OpenID and OAuth (described below), which can offer new ways of publishing and syndicating FOAF data. For example, FOAF, through an explicit evaluation of a web resource such as OpenID, can identify persons in the Web. FOAF as a core ontology, is currently used by many projects, such as Google Social Graph API and FOAF+SSL secure authentication protocol⁷² for building secure distributed social networks. The ontology is maintained by the Friend of a Friend (FOAF) project.

SIOC (Semantically Interlinked Online Communities) ontology⁷³

The SIOC initiative aims to enable the integration of online community information via an ontology for representing rich data, such as the content and structure of most online community sites - weblogs, bulletin boards, mailing lists, newsgroups, etc. SIOC can create new connections between discussion channels and posts, and allows users to browse discussion data in interesting ways using these connections. It can be used in conjunction with FOAF to express personal profile and social networking information. SIOC has become a popular way to express user-generated content and new kinds of usage scenarios for online communities by focusing on the description of the products of those communities (posts, blogs, replies, threads).

The SocIoS Object Model and the SocIoS Ontology⁷⁴

The SocIoS Object Model is at the core of the European project SocIoS (Exploiting Social Networks for Building the Future Internet of Services), and supports consistent operations (the SocIoS Core Services) to be performed on social media data, regardless of the social networking site from which the data is drawn.

⁷¹ FOAF-a-matic is a simple Javascript application by Leigh Dodds to create a FOAF description of a person, www.ldodds.com/foaf/foaf-a-matic

⁷² <http://notes.3kbo.com/foaf-ssl>

⁷³ Diego Berrueta *et al*, SIOC Core Ontology Specification, Uldis Bojārs, John G. Breslin (eds.), March 25, 2010, available at: <http://rdfs.org/sioc/spec/>, <http://sioc-project.org>

⁷⁴ <http://www.sociosproject.eu/Dissemination/Deliverables/tabid/119/language/en-GB/Default.aspx>

The SocIoS Core Services offer a service composition process, which transforms (via wrappers) the APIs (Application Programming Interfaces) currently provided by most social network platforms into services transparently incorporated in the service composition process.

As explained in Deliverable D2.3,⁷⁵ the SocIoS Object Model captures the set of datatypes (SocIoS objects) and the core APIs that act upon these datatypes (SocIoS Core Services). It is a formal specification which allows the unification of the underlying object models of the social platforms, capturing the most dominant concepts and their characteristics, and providing mechanisms to manage their entities in a unified way. The model is a close variation of OpenSocial Data Specification (see below), as developed by Google along with MySpace and a number of other social networks. The Object Model defines five core concepts that are directly mapped to entities that live in the underlying social networks:

Person; MediaItem; Activity; Message; Group

These are used to represent social platform users, content, activities, and short messages posted to other users and groups of users.

The SocIoS Object Model also provides an API which grants developers single point access to the underlying social platforms APIs, so that they can create applications to draw data from or perform actions on a wide range of these platforms without having to become familiar with their individual concepts, data structures and functions. Through the Object Model, users can invoke third party services accessible via the SocIoS platform, and combine them into new applications.

Figure 1. The simplified SocIoS ontology for Social Network Services (SNS)⁷⁶

Finally, the SocIoS Ontology presented in Deliverable 2.4⁷⁷ tries to describe semantically the elements of the SocIoS object model. It is a simplified ontology, which stems from the

⁷⁵ S. Porat, N. Ioannou, K. Tserpes, “SocIoS Object Model”, Deliverable D2.3, SocIoS project, FP7, 2011, <http://cordis.europa.eu/docs/projects/cnect/4/257774/080/deliverables/001-D23v10.pdf>

⁷⁶ Ibid., p. 23

analysis of the Social Network Services (SNS) world and their most common concepts; it focuses on defining the core objects that led to the definition of the object model. The figure above shows the simplified SocIoS ontology. Notice that *Person* and *MediaItem* are the central entities bound to the other core entities via relations.

Finally, the SocIoS researchers note the differences and similarities with FOAF and SIOC⁷⁸. Although FOAF's data specification is close to what SocIoS wants to achieve, FOAF is not meant to capture concepts that stem from the technical nature of the social platforms' APIs; for example capturing user activity is a central notion to SocIoS but does not exist as a concept in FOAF. Also, the core entity *Person* in SocIoS lists a person's characteristics and not its online connections as it is with FOAF. Similarly, SIOC is also close to SocIoS goals in terms of data specification compatibility. The difference here is that SIOC revolves around web communities and emphasises on forums rather than the social networking concepts. A typical example is "the lack of a detailed object to capture the notion of multimedia items and their sharing which are crucial to SocIoS."⁷⁹

It is to be noted here that both the FOAF and SIOC ontologies are also a means to increase credibility of postings in social media as they provide a way to correlate persons with their wider online presence in the virtual world.

2.2.4.3 Semantic models for crises

One of the areas where ontologies are particularly useful in populating semantic models is specialised fields with relatively limited vocabulary; crisis management being one such example. Indeed, a variety of researchers and practitioners have highlighted the need for open, commonly accepted (standardised) ontologies for such purposes⁸⁰. The variety of application specific ontologies, which have been developed for crisis information management to aid interoperability in specific scenarios, has been reviewed by Liu et al⁸¹ under the criteria of subject area coverage, design and current use, and conformance to standards.

The authors' research, which stemmed out of the European project Disaster 2.0,⁸² identified 11 critical subject areas as able to cover the information concepts needed for crisis management and a total of 26 relevant ontologies which represent these areas. Of those ontologies, 65% were considered as interoperable. The 11 subject areas identified are:

- Resources (material and human) – described by 3 ontologies
- Processes (procedures and tasks, such as search, rescue, etc) – described by 2 ontologies
- People – described by 2 ontologies
- Organisations, including working groups – described by 3 ontologies
- Damage (injuries, missing people, affected infrastructure, etc.) – described by 1 ontology

⁷⁷ K. Tserpes, "SocIoS ontology", Deliverable D2.4, SocIoS project, FP7, 2011, http://ec.europa.eu/information_society/apps/projects/logos/4/257774/080/deliverables/001_D24V10.pdf

⁷⁸ Ibid.

⁷⁹ Ibid.

⁸⁰ Di Maio, P, "An open ontology for open source emergency response systems", 2008, <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/summary?doi=10.1.1.93.1829>

⁸¹ Liu S., Brewster C., Shaw D., "Ontologies for Crisis Management: A Review of State of the Art in Ontology Design and Usability", Proceedings of the 10th International ISCRAM Conference – Baden-Baden, Germany, May 2013, T. Comes, F. Fiedrich, S. Fortier, J. Geldermann and L. Yang, eds.

⁸² Disaster 2.0 Project, EC Directorate-General Home Affairs, HOME/2010/CIPS/AG/002, <http://www.disaster20.eu>

- Disasters (natural, man-made, etc.) – described by 4 ontologies
- Infrastructure, physical and organisational – described by 3 ontologies
- Geography (geospatial information) – described by 1 ontology
- Hydrology (type of a water body, location, flow, etc.) – described by 1 ontology
- Meteorology (weather and climate information) – described by 1 ontology
- Topography, (surface shape, information on the terrain, ecological regime, etc) – described by 4 ontologies

Table 1 below, which also appears in COSMIC Deliverable 3.3.2 for completeness,⁸³ shows the 6 most relevant and comprehensive (from the point of view of crisis management) crisis ontologies (out of total of 26), their aim and the concepts they represent. They were chosen by Liu et al⁸¹ as being originally designed for crisis management. The authors note that SOKNOS,⁸⁴ ISyCri,⁸⁵ and WB-OS⁸⁶ are formally represented but not publicly available, (WS-OS is available upon request). In addition, they found that no formal ontologies are specifically intended for representing the emergency and disaster domain; existing ontologies that represent it are mainly in the form of not publicly available database schemas.

Table 1. Relevant crisis ontologies, aims and concepts they represent⁸⁷

Representative Crisis Ontologies	Types of Crisis Management Systems aimed for	Requirements of Information Representation
SOKNOS	Information integration for resource planning	Categorisation of damages and resources, deploy regulations defining the relations between them
SIADEx	Planning under uncertainty for decision support	Taxonomy of resources, legal information on the use of resources, operational targets and tasks for specific crisis scenarios, representation of uncertainty (temporal, resource and location)
ISyCri	Crisis response coordination	Categories of entities affected by crises, the treatment system, the crisis description
MOAC, HXL	Humanitarian disaster response and relief	Classification of damages, crises, response activities and resources; geo location about displaced persons
WB-OS	Web sites for disaster management	Features, components and information used to create disaster management web sites

Coverage of areas is according to the following:

- SOKNOS – resources, damage and disasters (3 areas)
- SIADEx⁸⁸ – resources, processes and geography (3 areas)

⁸³ Ioannis Kotsiopoulos, Angelos Yannopoulos, Hayley Watson, Kush Wadhwa, Susan Anson, Alex Papadimitriou, “Final report on the strategic use of emerging communication technologies for crisis stakeholders”, Deliverable D3.3.2, COSMIC project, October 2014, p.27, www.cosmic-project.eu

⁸⁴ Babitski, G., Probst, F., Hoffmann, J., Oberle, D., “Ontology design for information integration in disaster management”, Proceedings of the 4th International Workshop on Applications of Semantic Technologies (AST 2009), 2009

⁸⁵ Benaben, F., Hanachi, C., Lauras, M., Couget, P., Chapurlat, V., “A Metamodel and its Ontology to Guide Crisis Characterisation and its Collaborative Management”, Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Information Systems for Crisis Response and Management (ISCRAM 2008), Washington, DC, USA, 189-196, 2008

⁸⁶ Chen-Huei, C., Zahedi, F.M., Huimin, Z., “Ontology for Developing Web Sites for Natural Disaster Management: Methodology and Implementation”, Systems, Man and Cybernetics, Part A: Systems and Humans, IEEE Transactions on, 41, 1, 50-62, 2011

⁸⁷Liu S., Brewster C., Shaw D., “Ontologies for Crisis Management: A Review of State of the Art in Ontology Design and Usability”, Proceedings of the 10th International ISCRAM Conference – Baden-Baden, Germany, May 2013, T. Comes, F. Fiedrich, S. Fortier, J. Geldermann and L. Yang, eds., Table 2

- ISyCri – processes, damages and disasters (3 areas)
- MOAC (Management Of A Crisis)^{89, 90} – resources, processes, damage and disasters (4 areas)
- HXL (Humanitarian eXchange Language)⁹¹ – damage, geography, organisation and disasters (4 areas)
- WB-OS – processes⁹²

There are no common or widely accepted standards used in these crisis ontologies. Liu et al mention only three out of the six ontologies of Table 1 as being related to standards:

- SOKNOS, which follows the principles of DOLCE foundational ontology⁹³
- MOAC, which conforms to de-facto standards developed by the Inter Agency Standing Committee (IASC), the Emergency Shelter Cluster in Haiti, the 3W database⁹⁴ and the Ushahidi Haiti Project⁹⁵
- HXL, which links to the OGC GeoSPARQL standard for defining geo location vocabularies

The above analysis indicates the lack of a common vocabulary or standard for the domain. We perceive this would be one of the hardest goals to meet since it would be a significant challenge to achieve the consensus across all the stakeholders. Moreover, it may not be feasible to share a single domain ontology by various applications as useful domain ontologies are designed for the particular tasks they target. However, it would be feasible to specify terminologies for interoperability gaps that are crucial and have not been addressed yet.

The conclusion drawn by the authors (Liu et al) of the above mentioned review paper on existing ontologies for crisis management is that it is an active but fragmented field, with a shortage of formal ontologies, missing terminologies and interoperability gaps. There is a lack of a common vocabulary or standard for the domain, and, as usual in such cases, achieving consensus across all stakeholders would be challenging, to say the least. The authors also recognise the difficulty of sharing a single domain ontology by various applications; instead they propose the specification of terminologies for interoperability gaps that are crucial and have not been addressed yet. Similar remarks have been made by Carsten Keßler and Chad

⁸⁸ de la Asunción, M., Castillo, L., Fdez-Olivares, J., García-Pérez, O., González, A., Palao, F., “SIADEx: An interactive knowledge-based planner for decision support in forest fire fighting, *AI Commun.*, 18, 4, 257-268, 2005

⁸⁹ Management Of A Crisis (MOAC) vocabulary, 2012 specification, <http://observedchange.com/moac/ns>

⁹⁰ Benaben, F., Hanachi, C., Lauras, M., Couget, P., Chapurlat, V., “A Metamodel and its Ontology to Guide Crisis Characterization and its Collaborative Management”, *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Information Systems for Crisis Response and Management (ISCRAM 2008)*, Washington, DC, USA, 189-196, 2008

⁹¹ Carsten Keßler, Chad Hendrix, “The Humanitarian eXchange Language: Coordinating Disaster Response with Semantic Web Technologies”, *Semantic Web Journal 1* (2009) 1–5, IOS Press, 2013, http://www.semantic-web-journal.net/system/files/swj537_0.pdf

⁹² This ontology contains web elements which a government website should have so as to serve disaster management. From that point of view it covers the process area as relates to the way (process) of building relevant government web sites.

⁹³ Babitski, G., Probst, F., Hoffmann, J., Oberle, D., “Ontology design for information integration in disaster management”, *Proceedings of the 4th International Workshop on Applications of Semantic Technologies (AST 2009)*, 2009

⁹⁴ Who does What Where (3W), Contact Management Directory, UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), <http://3w.unocha.org/WhoWhatWhere>

⁹⁵ <http://www.ushahidi.com/2011/04/19/ushahidi-haiti-project-evaluation-final-report>

Hendrix, who observe that “while the use of Semantic Web technology for disaster management has been discussed in the literature⁹⁶, the proposal for Crowdsourced Linked Open Data⁹⁷ is the only actual application to date”, where information about the Haiti earthquake collected on the Ushahidi platform was organised and made available online, using the Management Of A Crisis (MOAC) vocabulary developed for this purpose (see ref. footnote ⁸⁹). The authors also point out that synergies between the different efforts (such as those above to use Semantic Web technologies in crises) are under discussion in the recently established Emergency Information Community Group of W3C.⁹⁸

The Ushahidi Haiti Project (UHP) – Open source participatory information gathering⁹⁹

“We all know – I hope – that the Ushahidi Haiti Project was far from perfect and this point is reiterated again in this evaluation. Yet, this project is significant in that it is one small part of a paradigm shift. Lives were saved – this is true and a point that cannot be overstated. And yet many of the significant results of this project are not seen in the immediate effects, but in the long-term influence that the initiative had in proving that open-source, participatory information gathering can work.”

In response to the above findings, researchers of Project Disaster 2.0¹⁰⁰ created the formal ontology DiRes in the aim to cover the identified key interoperability gaps of existing ontologies. DiRes describes emergency and disaster events, and the key factors associated with disaster response activities¹⁰¹. DiRes defines terms relating to disasters (what has happened), operations (what can be done), people and organisation (who are involved and take actions), resources (what are needed and used), time and location (when and where), and the damage that a disaster has caused. DiRes specialises the Friend of a Friend (FOAF) ontology¹⁰², the W3C Organisation ontology¹⁰³ and the Open Geospatial Consortium GeoSPARQL ontology¹⁰⁴ in order to describe correspondingly people from different governmental agencies and organisations, the origin place and boundary of a disaster event, and the check-in location of a disaster response operation by first responders and aid agencies.

The specification of DiRes is still evolving and its wider acceptance is dependent on a variety of factors ranging from policy (for example the fragmentation observed in the EU) to ease of use and to added adoption by governmental and non-governmental organisations.¹⁰⁵

⁹⁶ Eva Blomqvist, “The use of Semantic Web technologies for decision support – a survey”, Semantic Web Journal, IOS Press, Volume 5, Number 3, 2014

⁹⁷ Jens Ortmann, Minu Limbu, Dong Wang, and Tomi Kauppinen, “Crowdsourcing Linked Open Data for Disaster Management”, in Rolf Grütter, Dave Kolas, Manolis Koubarakis, Dieter Pfoser (eds), Proceedings of Terra Cognita 2011, Workshop at the 10th International Semantic Web Conference, (ISWC2011), volume 798 of CEUR Workshop Proceedings, Bonn, Germany, October 2011.

⁹⁸ Souripriya Das, Seema Sundara, Richard Cyganiak, “R2RML: RDB to RDF Mapping Language”, W3C recommendation available from <http://www.w3.org/TR/r2rml>, 27 September 2012.

⁹⁹ Chrissy Martin, “Ushahidi Haiti Project Evaluation Final Report”, article reproduced by Patrick Meier on Ushahidi, 19 April 2011, <http://www.ushahidi.com/2011/04/19/ushahidi-haiti-project-evaluation-final-report>

¹⁰⁰ Disaster 2.0 Project, EC Directorate-General Home Affairs, HOME/2010/CIPS/AG/002, <http://www.disaster20.eu>

¹⁰¹ Ibid., <http://www.disaster20.eu/dires>

¹⁰² <http://xmlns.com/foaf/spec>

¹⁰³ <http://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-org>

¹⁰⁴ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/geosparql>

¹⁰⁵ This short description of the DiRes ontology has also been included in COSMIC Deliverable D3.3.2 under section 3.3 on semantic interoperability

On another note, the UN OCHA initiative HXL (The Humanitarian eXchange Language) is continuously evolving towards becoming a standard for operational semantically-rich data (ontology) in the humanitarian domain. We refer to section 2.2.6 for more details.

Need for further research.

Following the commentary in this section, what appears to be of interest is that we have two different streams of evolution in the wider field of semantic interoperability and the corresponding open standardisation: social media and crisis management. We have shown throughout COSMIC that the former plays an important role in the success of the latter, but we are aware of no research effort to address the common ground of both streams (i.e. semantic interoperability for social media in crisis management), with the notable exception of the Crowdsourced Linked Open Data application mentioned above (ref. footnote ⁹⁷). This is an area of further research, which can result in useful applications with life-saving potential.

2.2.5 Standardisation of the technical means for interacting with social media services

In this sub-section, we describe a whole stack of technologies for interacting with social media services¹⁰⁶. We cover an open source technology stack, which provides a reasonable basis for a standardisation of tools for interacting with social media services. The negative side of this choice is that some of the technologies described have not been adopted by Facebook and Twitter – for example, OpenSocial. These social media “majors” often use proprietary standards that only work with their own services (although their precise practices fluctuate over time). We have a clear example of market leaders trying to lock potential competitors out of the market by avoiding standardisation, as discussed in the beginning of this chapter. On the other hand, it can also be argued that the open standards are being promoted by Facebook and Twitter competitors who would use such standards as a wedge to let themselves into a business created by Facebook and Twitter and largely ignored by them until too late – these competitors include Google, Yahoo! and IBM. While the open standards are definitely the preferable solution in general, the motivations of companies for supporting them or avoiding them are thus quite complicated and not trivial to judge morally.

The major set of open source technologies specifications include:

- OpenSocial¹⁰⁷
 - OpenSocial supports exploring the social graph and application development for social media applications. *“OpenSocial is a public specification that defines a component hosting environment (container) and a set of common application programming interfaces (APIs) for web-based applications. It can be used as a general-use runtime environment for allowing untrusted and partially trusted components from third parties to run in an existing web application. OpenSocial is the most mature standards-based component model for cloud based social apps. Using OpenSocial, it is easy to develop an app that reaches users in their activity stream, in content, in email, or even on their mobile device.”*

¹⁰⁶ following the organisation of material in: LeBlanc, Jonathan, “Programming Social Applications: Building Viral Experiences with OpenSocial, OAuth, OpenID, and Distributed Web Frameworks”, O’Reilly Media, Inc., 2011

¹⁰⁷ <http://opensocial.org>

The latest version, OpenSocial 2.0, has incorporated support for the Activity Streams community specification.

- Shindig¹⁰⁸
 - Apache Shindig is a *container implementation* for OpenSocial. It is a framework for web-based applications. It provides a reference implementation for the OpenSocial standard, covering both the server-side and the client-side. It addresses the rendering of OpenSocial gadgets inside the web browser. Its goal is to enable the very easy and fast implementation work required for sites to host social apps.
- OAuth¹⁰⁹
 - OAuth is an open standard, defining an open authentication protocol. *“It allows secure authorization in a simple and standard method from web, mobile and desktop applications. OAuth is an open standard for authorization. OAuth provides a method for clients to access server resources on behalf of a resource owner (such as a different client or an end-user). It also provides a process for end-users to authorize third-party access to their server resources without sharing their credentials (typically, a username and password pair), using user-agent redirections.”*
- OpenID¹¹⁰
 - *“OpenID is an open standard that allows users to be authenticated by certain co-operating sites (known as Relying Parties or RP) using a third party service, eliminating the need for webmasters to provide their own ad hoc systems and allowing users to consolidate their digital identities. Users may create accounts with their preferred OpenID identity providers, and then use those accounts as the basis for signing on to any website which accepts OpenID authentication. The OpenID standard provides a framework for the communication that must take place between the identity provider and the OpenID acceptor (the "relying party").”*
- Caja¹¹¹ and ADSafe¹¹²
 - These are tools enabling the safe execution of frontend code. For example, ads executing code in the end user’s browser can be made safe using these tools, so that ads can be trusted to promote products or services to users, without fear of introducing malware or having other adverse effects on the user’s computer.
- The Open Graph protocol¹¹³
 - The Open Graph protocol supports the *exploration* of social web entities. *“The Open Graph protocol enables any web page to become a rich object in a social graph. For instance, this is used on Facebook to allow any web page to have the same functionality as any other object on Facebook. While many different technologies and schemas exist and could be combined together, there isn't a single technology which provides enough information to richly represent any web page within the social graph. The Open Graph protocol builds on these existing technologies and gives developers one thing to implement.”*
- Activity Streams¹¹⁴

¹⁰⁸ <http://shindig.apache.org>

¹⁰⁹ <http://oauth.net/>

¹¹⁰ <http://openid.net>

¹¹¹ <http://code.google.com/p/google-caja>

¹¹² <http://www.adsafe.org>

¹¹³ <http://ogp.me>

¹¹⁴ <http://activitystrea.ms>

- *“Activity Streams is a foundation for delivering activity content. Activity Streams is an open format specification for activity stream protocols, which are used to syndicate activities taken in social web applications and services, similar to those in Facebook’s Newsfeed, FriendFeed, the Movable Type Action Streams plugin, etc. An activity stream is a list of recent activities performed by an individual, typically on a single website.”*
- WebFinger¹¹⁵
 - *“WebFinger is a means of discovering public user data using email addresses. WebFinger is a protocol that allows for discovery of information about people and things identified by a URI.”*
- OExchange¹¹⁶
 - *“OExchange an open protocol for sharing any URL with any service on the Web.”*
- PubSubHubbub¹¹⁷
 - *“PubSubHubbub is a means of syndicating user conversations from a root provider to multiple subscribers. PubSubHubbub is a simple, open, server-to-server webhook-based pubsub (publish/subscribe) protocol for any web accessible resources. Parties (servers) speaking the PubSubHubbub protocol can get near-instant notifications (via webhook callbacks) when a topic (resource URL) they’re interested in is updated.”*
- The Salmon protocol¹¹⁸
 - *“The Salmon protocol is a message exchange taking the foundation of PubSubHubbub and unifying conversations between publishers and subscribers. It is a protocol running over HTTP designed to decentralize commentary and annotations made against newsfeed articles such as blog posts. It allows a single discussion thread to be established between the article’s origin and any feed reader or “aggregator” which is subscribing to the content. Put simply, that if an article appeared on 3 sites A (the source), B and C (the aggregates), that members of all 3 sites could see and contribute to a single thread of conversation regardless of site they were viewing from.”*

In what follows, we present examples of the standardisation effort at two different international organisations, with differing missions. These are the United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) and the World Wide Web Consortium, otherwise known as W3C.¹¹⁹ The former is a crisis response organisation, while the latter is a standardisation organisation organised as a community. Their common point, with regard to social networks is that they both, through the need to serve their purpose, recognise the necessity for standardisation in social media and work actively towards its achievement.

2.2.6 The standardisation effort at OCHA

The Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) is the United Nations’ division responsible for the orchestration of response actions to disastrous events such as the 2010 Haiti earthquake and the recent armed conflict in Mali. OCHA, by its nature, has to coordinate a large number of organisations in the field, often amongst confusing situations in

¹¹⁵ <http://code.google.com/p/webfinger>

¹¹⁶ <http://www.oexchange.org>

¹¹⁷ <http://code.google.com/p/pubsubhubbub>

¹¹⁸ <http://www.salmon-protocol.org>

¹¹⁹ <http://www.w3.org>

the affected regions. In 2011 the idea of a common exchange format for humanitarian data was brought up within OCHA so as to facilitate data sharing with OCHA and other collaborators, while allowing organisations to retain their established data management practices. An approach based on Semantic Web technologies was finally chosen, which resulted in the formation of the Humanitarian eXchange Language (HXL) initiative and the corresponding vocabulary. The aim is that HXL will continue to evolve and eventually become a standard for operational data in the humanitarian domain.

Following a recent account of its status by Carsten Keßler and Chad Hendrix,¹²⁰ at the present stage of development, the HXL vocabulary formalises established terminology from the domain, with a focus on humanitarian profile data and core reference data, such as geographic information. HXL data already drive the first applications, including emergency dashboards and a Web service infrastructure for geographic information. The HXL vocabulary will be gradually extended as required, depending on the next reference datasets to be included. An initial data governance system has been set up to ensure that any data coming in from the field are approved at the cluster lead level before publication.

Defining the HXL vocabulary for the humanitarian system as a whole clearly goes beyond the capabilities and expertise of OCHA and mappings to other initiatives such as AGROVOC,¹²¹ the International Aid Transparency Initiative (IATI)¹²², and others¹²³ are planned, along with a provision for HXL links to existing vocabularies outside the humanitarian domain.

Regarding the fate of HXL in standardisation, Carsten Keßler and Chad Hendrix note that the amount of feedback and interest they receive from the humanitarian domain shows that *“a more comprehensive solution is required. The biggest obstacle we currently see for the adoption of HXL is the lack of developers familiar with Semantic Web technologies. A graph-based model adds a steep learning curve for programmers who mostly deal with relational data models.”* To alleviate the difficulty, they report that work is currently done on an easy-to-use RESTful API layer on top of the SPARQL endpoint that enables straightforward access to frequently requested data.

Besides HXL, other standardisation-like activities of OCHA include the 3W Database, also used by the MOAC ontology (see section 2.2.4.3) and the very recent study on hashtag standards for emergencies. The 3W Database was created to retrieve key information to assess and ensure that humanitarian needs are met in crises such that: which organisations (Who) are carrying out what activities (What) and in which locations (Where). The database (3W) has been universally agreed as being the most important priority for any co-ordination activity and is accompanied by the integrated Contact Management Directory¹²⁴, which makes for easy navigation by users.

¹²⁰ Carsten Keßler, Chad Hendrix, “The Humanitarian eXchange Language: Coordinating Disaster Response with Semantic Web Technologies”, *Semantic Web Journal* 1 (2009) 1–5, IOS Press, 2013, http://www.semantic-web-journal.net/system/files/swj537_0.pdf

¹²¹ Boris Lauser, Margherita Sini, “From AGROVOC to the Agricultural Ontology Service/Concept Server: An OWL Model for Creating Ontologies in the Agricultural Domain”, in *Proceedings of the 2006 International Conference on Dublin Core and Metadata Applications: Metadata for Knowledge and Learning, DCMI '06*, pages 76–88. Dublin Core Metadata Initiative, 2006

¹²² <http://support.iatistandard.org/categories/20001338-The-IATI-Standards>

¹²³ Tim Davies, Duncan Edwards, “Emerging Implications of Open and Linked Data for Knowledge Sharing in Development”, *IDS Bulletin*, 43(5):117–127, 2012

¹²⁴ Who does What Where (3W), Contact Management Directory, UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), <http://3w.unocha.org/WhoWhatWhere>

Another initiative by OCHA is a proposal for the standardisation of hashtags¹²⁵, which are already used in Twitter. Hashtags generally allow researchers, emergency responders and affected community members to identify Twitter conversations related to a given topic. Due to this property, there have been previous but unsuccessful standardisation efforts. The report notes that despite widespread pleas encouraging standardisation activities for disaster relief (nine reports by the ITU alone)¹²⁶, standardisation needs in social media monitoring have not been addressed.

Figure 2. Tracking Hurricane Sandy news through Twitter¹²⁷

Based on examples, such as the use of the Twitter hashtag platform to help news reporters, response teams and the public have a better understanding of Hurricane Sandy’s impact along the United States east coast (see example below), the report proposes that emergency response agencies encourage standardisation of three types of hashtags during a crisis:

- a disaster name hashtag
- a public reporting hashtag
- an emergency response hashtag

Each hashtag is intended to fulfil a specific role, such as to ensure the continuity of information, to enable public tracking of needs, people and supplies and to provide a platform to facilitate direct assistance. The proposal has been subjected to pilot use in the current Ebola virus crisis, as shown below.

Hashtag standards to support the Ebola response¹²⁸

¹²⁵ “Hashtag standards for emergencies”, UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), OCHA Policy and Studies Series, OCHA, October 2014, 12

¹²⁶ International Telecommunications Union (ITU):

- “Disaster Relief Systems, Network Resilience and Recovery: Technical Reports Published” ituneslog, 6 August 2014, <http://newslog.itu.int/archives/579>, and
- “N.R.a.R. FG-DR&NRR Technical Reports”, Focus Group on Disaster Relief Systems, 2014, <http://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/focusgroups/dnrnr/Pages/default.aspx>

¹²⁷ Sullivan, D., “Tracking Hurricane Sandy News Through Twitter”, 2012

¹²⁸ “Hashtag standards for emergencies”, UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), OCHA Policy and Studies Series, OCHA, October 2014, 12, page 10

“Humanitarian IMO (@hum_IM) is a Twitter account that connects OCHA information management officers. It recently integrated the above-mentioned ideas to support the West Africa Ebola response (see next figure). #EbolaLR, #EbolaSL and #EbolaGN are examples of disaster-naming hashtag standards. #EbolaResponse and #EbolaNeed are examples of public reporting hashtag standards. The dissemination of this information is integrated into an infographic for easy sharing and to prevent the disruption of hashtag monitoring. The publication encourages the geo-location of the message, thus further enabling analyses.”

Figure 3. Integrated Ebola example (disaster name hashtag, public reporting hashtag, infographic and GPS)¹²⁹

The authors are cautious and warn on possible misuse of such a system. Introducing single-use or episodic hashtags may result in use of Twitter for small-scale emergencies in place of traditional emergency phone lines. Also, use of such a platform may be more limited than expected due to the presence of various forms of the digital divide in societies.

Finally, the report argues that, with Twitter being particularly suited to emergencies due to its robustness and micro-blogging facilities, by encouraging more standardisation, and therefore more structure in tweets, agencies can help support analyses and stave off big-data challenges. This can improve the signal-to-noise ratio in emergencies and alleviate a part of the load falling on current researchers who strive for complex algorithms to extract emergency-related information from existing tweets.

2.2.7 W3C: towards social standards

W3C has a long standing interest in social networks and the wider field called social business, when it comes to business opportunities. Its defining event was the W3C Social Business Jam event in 2011, which resulted in a report on the state of social business and future directions. It was the first purely "online" event to explore possible space for standardisation to enable the social web for business use-cases. In line with any W3C workshop, the Social Business Jam was an online conversation amongst representatives in business, government and technology, which resulted in a number of important recommendations, such as the formation of a W3C Social Business Community Group in order to develop a number of customer-driven strategic use-cases for standardising the Social Web.

¹²⁹ Ibid., Figure 8, page 10

A more recent development (2013) was that W3C coordinated with the OpenSocial Foundation in order to produce standards directly focusing on social media. The objective of the collaboration was to “make social a first-class citizen of the Web”, by developing open, royalty-free standards and patents under the respected W3C brand, ensuring the quality and interoperability of social media services, applications and data, and promoting competition in the social media industry to focus on the innovation and value of services provided, rather than in customer lock-in. An emphasis was to be placed on reliability and availability, focusing on the business potential of social media; however these properties are also critical for crisis management, since unreliable or unevenly available communications tools during a crisis are a serious problem.

The report of a workshop on this topic, held in San Francisco in August 2013,¹³⁰ confirmed the objectives of the collaboration and contributed to the realisation of the formation of the Community and Social Business Group¹³¹ (called for by the Social Business Jam report). The Group has a mission to focus on social business use-cases and on the application of those use-cases to standards, standards improvements, and standards gaps. Initial conversations will be based on the W3C Jam Results recommendations,¹³² but the group will not produce specifications. Further evolution of the Group into say a Working Group within W3C may enable it to develop draft specifications according to the next steps of the Jam report¹³³, which recommended five areas in which social media draft specifications should be developed.

W3C recommendations for draft standards specifications for social media¹³⁴

“... ”

- **Social Business Process:** *Given that "walled garden" social networks for Business Process Management only create additional integration issues for the rest of the business and exclude those not using BPM tools from discussions, some of the existing Business Process Management standards such as WF-XML, BPEL (BEPL4People, WS-HumanTask, etc.), the proposed Case Management extensions (www.omg.org), and status APIs should be leveraged for effective integration into social platforms, which will likely be built around the OStatus stack.*
- **Prioritization Extensions for ActivityStreams:** *ActivityStreams needs a way to mark activities as “required” (where a “required” activity is one that must be opened, read and reviewed by the recipient) as well as a way to deal with prioritization issues in general. Currently, marking activities in an activity stream as “required” is not available through the activity streams specification. Yet prioritization is "user-centric" insofar as an activity required for one person may not be required for another, so the prioritization may be the result of an interaction with a user identity rather than part of the message payload. There are also questions around how to handle a required activity once it has been opened, reviewed, and possibly acted upon by the user, as well as a lack of agreement of how priorities are represented and how to convey priority between different social technologies such as e-mail.*
- **ActivityStreams Analytics Extensions:** *Analytics are typically used on the consumer side of social technologies to better understand customer buying habits, interests, web viewing*

¹³⁰ W3C-OpenSocial, Workshop report, Workshop on Social Standards: The Future of Business, 7-8 August 2013, San Francisco, USA, <http://www.w3.org/2013/socialweb/report>

¹³¹ W3C Community and Social Business Group, <http://www.w3.org/community/socbizcg>

¹³² W3C Social Business Jam event, November 8-10, 2011, <http://www.w3.org/2011/socialbusiness-jam/report.html>

¹³³ Ibid.

¹³⁴ Ibid., section “Next Steps”

habits, but can be extended to be part of the non-customer side of analytics – helping employees understand and digest activity streams used for running the business. Yet even basic technologies such as text search are insufficient, especially when a user cannot remember specific key words, dates or other details around a conversation. Developing analytics standards on top of ActivityStreams that help users process a “reference library” of social conversations was seen as an important step.

- **Social Metric Specification:** *Metrics were viewed as an essential ingredient in measuring the effectiveness of social technologies, but there is neither consistency in how metric data is represented between various social technologies nor understanding in how this data can be exchanged outside of proprietary solutions; there is little understanding of how to gather and share metrics in a federated social web environment. The scale of metrics, guidelines on how they can be appropriately displayed to users, and how to transmit them need to be explored.*
- **Social E-Mail Enhancements:** *Although the web is moving to activity streams, the primary business communication tool of choice is e-mail, and so there are needs to be significantly tighter integration of newer social technologies with e-mail. It was a consensus in among jam participants that e-mail should not be viewed as legacy technology to be replaced by newer social technologies, but that as it is the primary business communication tool of choice, it should be integrated with newer social technologies. So the concept of social e-mail goes beyond embedding widgets or gadgets in a page that shows both activity streams and e-mail, but a truly social mail should allow messages to automatically be converted to and from other social formats depending on the desired medium of communication. The OStatus draft recommendation could be extended to include appropriate interfaces with the SMTP/IMAP/POP standards. Social e-mail should also be a data-source for new draft analytics specifications, allowing for users to more easily reference, share, catalog and analyze e-mails and include e-mail as artifacts in business process and defect tracking systems.”*

With strategy having been decided to follow the above recommendations, considerable steps towards the interoperability among social platforms’ services can be achieved. Although there is no current mandate for work on the above specification, and therefore no usable output yet available, should the intended progress towards social standards be achieved, the positive impact on crisis management can be considerable.

2.3 CONCLUSION

In this chapter, existing policies, standards and opportunities relating to social media and crises were identified. Applicable legislative measures taken at EU level cover the areas of privacy, data protection and telecommunications. The partners highlighted the relevance of the reform of the current Data Protection Directive (1992), proposed by the European Commission, and, in particular, its provision for added protection of online data via the “right to oblivion” (Article 17). On the telecommunications side, the implications of the, as yet unsettled, issue of the lack of an EU-wide imposed minimum bandwidth obligation on a Universal Provider were noted as a pending policy issue potentially affecting social network based communication, especially during a crisis.

The question of standardisation in social media was found to affect aspects such as compatibility, interoperability, safety and quality both from the point of view of the industry as well as consumers. The partners examined standardisation challenges such as the

underlying telecommunications technologies, the presentation layer of social media, the data involved and the means of interacting with social media services. For the semantics-rich social media data, representation mechanisms such as Linked Data were identified and commented upon, along with various emerging attempts for describing semantic models.

Finally, examination of the developing and varied landscape of tools for interacting with social media services revealed the complex interplay between market leaders and their competitors and correspondingly between proprietary and open standards. We also referred to the standardisation effort at two international organisations, with differing missions. These were the United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) and the World Wide Web Consortium, otherwise known as W3C. The former is a crisis response organisation, while the latter is a standardisation organisation organised as a community. Their common point, with regard to social networks is that they both, through the need to serve their purpose, recognise the necessity for standardisation in social media and work actively towards its achievement.

DRAFT

3 CHALLENGES POSED BY PRIVACY, SECURITY AND ACTIVISM

There are a number of inherent challenges to be taken into consideration if those involved in crisis management activities are to optimally use emerging technologies as part of their efforts in preparing for and responding to crises involving the security of citizens. This chapter seeks to examine those challenges relating to privacy, security and citizens' activism concerning the use of social media in crisis management. Such privacy related challenges include: right and expectation of privacy, privacy protection for individuals, adhering to key EU data protection principles, informed consent, transparency, proportionality and legitimate purpose, anonymity and surveillance.

Increased connectivity enabled by social media also provides opportunities for social activism. Partners have reviewed secondary data regarding recent social movements to outline how social media facilitate mobilisation, transnational communication and organisation of activist networks.

Partners will also touch upon security related challenges, including: the protection, reliability and accuracy of information and the risk of vigilante justice.

In order to do so, partners have conducted desk-based research to explore relevant literature including news articles (including blog posts), industry reports, project reports and peer-reviewed journal articles relating to some of the privacy, security and activism challenges that are relevant to the use of social media in emergency situations.

3.1 PRIVACY

As extensively discussed and scrutinised within policy, the press and the academic arena, privacy often appears as a key concern in relation to new and emerging technologies, including social media.¹³⁵ The concept “privacy” is notoriously difficult to define. Solove argues that privacy is best understood as a “family of different yet related things”.¹³⁶ In 1997, Roger Clarke outlined a taxonomy of four different types of privacy: privacy of the person, privacy of personal data, privacy of personal behaviour and privacy of personal communication.¹³⁷ More than a decade later, Finn, Wright and Friedewald updated Clarke's categories to include three additional types of privacy including; privacy of thoughts and feelings, privacy of location and space and privacy of association (including group privacy).¹³⁸ Such privacy considerations are relevant, particularly when considering the use of social media by stakeholders, including members of the public, in various types of crisis situations. Accordingly, with an increasing emphasis being placed on the use of social media for different stages of emergency management, it is necessary for stakeholders to consider the many privacy related challenges that they may need to confront, particularly: relevant EU

¹³⁵ Watson, Hayley, and Rachel L. Finn, “Privacy and ethical implications of the use of social media during a volcanic eruption: some initial thoughts”, *Proceedings of the 10th International ISCRAM Conference*, Baden-Baden, Germany, May 2013.

¹³⁶ Solove, Daniel J., *Understanding Privacy*, Harvard University Press, Cambridge MA and London, 2008. [p. 9]

¹³⁷ Clarke, Roger, “Introduction to Dataveillance and Information Privacy, and Definitions of Terms”, Xamax Consultancy, Aug 1997. <http://www.rogerclarke.com/DV/Intro.html>

¹³⁸ Finn, Rachel L., David Wright and Michael Friedewald, “Seven types of privacy”, in Serge Gutwirth, Yves Pouillet et al. (eds.), *European Data Protection: Coming of Age*, Springer, Dordrecht, 2013.

policy, principles relating to data protection, anonymity and other privacy related considerations, particularly in relation to surveillance.

3.1.1 Right and expectation of privacy

Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) protects the private life of individuals against arbitrary interference by public authorities and private organisations such as the media. It covers four distinct areas: private life, family life, home and correspondence. Article 8 is a qualified right, so in certain circumstances public authorities can interfere with the private and family life of an individual. These circumstances are set out in Article 8(2). Such interference must be proportionate, in accordance with law and necessary to protect national security, public safety or the economic well-being of the country; to prevent disorder or crime, protect health or morals, or to protect the rights and freedoms of others. Public authorities and private organisations should take all steps to ensure that they fulfil their obligations under Article 8 of the ECHR. This is to take into account how the European Court of Human Rights has consistently held that the storing and retention of personal data by police or national security authorities constitutes an interference with Article 8 (1) of the ECHR.¹³⁹

3.1.2 Adequate protection of an individual's personal data

Under EU law, data protection has been acknowledged as a fundamental right.¹⁴⁰ One of the most prominent privacy related issue to consider in relation to engagement with social media as a tool for crisis management activities is the challenge of ensuring that an individual's personal data is adequately protected. As discussed in Chapter 2 of this report, the protection of personal data is of utmost concern to the EU, as indicated by Article 8 "Protection of personal data" within the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (2000/C 364/01); "everyone has a right to the protection of personal data".¹⁴¹ This is also evidenced via the current legal framework, Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC. However, the right to data protection is not an absolute right and should be considered in relation to its function in society.¹⁴²

Ensuring the adequate protection of data collected or received from others is a crucial challenge that affects all stakeholders involved in using social media as part of their crisis management activities. Within the EU (including all countries of the European Economic Area – EEA, as well as Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway), data protection involves the adequate protection and use of an individual's personal data. For instance, under the Directive 95/46/EC, Art. 6 outlines principles of data protection, Art. 10 and 11 specify information to be given to the data subject, Art. 12 outlines individual's rights of access to their data and Art. 17 states that an individual's personal data should be protected from misuse and unauthorised

¹³⁹ See, for example, ECtHR, *Leander v. Sweden*, No. 9248/81, 26 March 1987; ECtHR, *M.M. v. the United Kingdom*, No. 24029/07, 13 November 2012; ECtHR, *M.K. v. France*, No. 19522/09, 18 April 2013; ECtHR, *B.B. v. France*, No. 5335/06, 17 December 2009; ECtHR, *S. and Marper v. the United Kingdom*, Nos. 30562/04 and 30566/04, 4 December 2008; ECtHR, *Allan v. the United Kingdom*, No. 48539/99, 5 November 2002

¹⁴⁰ For a comprehensive oversight of European data protection law, see the European Agency for Fundamental Rights, *Handbook on European data protection law*, Publications office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2014.

¹⁴¹ "Charter of fundamental rights of the European Union", *Official Journal of the European Communities*, 2000/C 364/01, 18 December 2000. http://www.europarl.europa.eu/charter/pdf/text_en.pdf

¹⁴² CJEU, Joined cases C-92/09 and C-93/09 *Volker and Marcus Scheke GbR and Hartmut Eifert v. Land Hessen*, 9 November 2010, para 48.

disclosure or access.¹⁴³ These, and other Articles in the Directive, set out the parameters with which personal data should lawfully be protected.

When taking this Directive into consideration for crisis management activities involving the collection of data, it is therefore necessary to consider the legal implications of data mining activities. Furthermore, there is a need for the consideration of other national privacy related laws that may impact the use of systems to alert individuals. For instance, in 2009, Federal privacy laws in Australia restricted private (telephone) numbers from being accessed by emergency services. Consequently, following deadly wildfires in Victoria, Australia in February 2009 where 181 people were killed, thousands of people were left unprepared as officials were still trying to deal with the challenges imposed on them by privacy laws, which restricted them from installing a nationwide fire alert telephone system.¹⁴⁴

Accordingly, considering the various legal restrictions and requirements and ensuring that adequate data protection policies are implemented as part of an organisations collection and re-use of data is an important and complex challenge to be met. Examples in data protection practices can be seen in the recommendations of the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC), who assert that: “Protection actors setting up systematic information collection through the Internet or other media must analyse the different potential risks linked to the collection, sharing or public display of the information and adapt the way they collect, manage and publicly release the information accordingly”.¹⁴⁵ One means of making this assessment is by conducting a privacy impact assessment (PIA).

A PIA is a tool that can be used by organisations to identify and reduce the privacy risks of projects (the GDPR speaks of data protection impact assessments). According to the UK Information Commissioner’s Office (ICO), a PIA can “reduce the risks of harm to individuals through the misuse of their personal information” and help design “more efficient and effective processes for handling personal data”.¹⁴⁶ Organisations may conduct the PIA internally using guides produced by national data protection authorities or hire a third party organisation providing such services to conduct such an assessment. As examined by the “A Privacy Impact Assessment Framework for data protection and privacy rights” (PIAF) project, once such example (among others) of a PIA was that carried out by Google Street View.¹⁴⁷ Following Google’s filming and collection of open Wi-Fi information from unsecured Wi-Fi networks in New Zealand in 2008, the New Zealand Privacy Commissioner referred the case to the police in June 2010, where following an enquiry it was found that Google had failed to adequately notify the public of its activities and had breached the Privacy Act 1993. In the outcome of the case Google was forced to carry out a PIA. Findings from PIAFF demonstrate shortcomings with the PIA carried out by Google, particularly in its

¹⁴³ “DIRECTIVE 95/46/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data”, *Official Journal*, L 281, 23 November 1995.

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX:31995L0046:en:HTML>

¹⁴⁴ “Police detain 2 about wildfires”, *The Associate Press, The Jakarta Post*, 12 February 2009.

<http://www.thejakartapost.com/news/2009/02/12/australian-police-detain-2-about-wildfires.html>

¹⁴⁵ ICRC, “Professional standards for Protection Work ICRC: carried out by humanitarian and human rights actors in armed conflict and other situations of violence”, *International Committee of the Red Cross*, Geneva, Switzerland, 2013. <https://www.icrc.org/eng/resources/documents/publication/p0999.htm> [p. 86.]

¹⁴⁶ ICO, *Privacy Impact Assessment*, no date.

http://ico.org.uk/for_organisations/data_protection/topic_guides/privacy_impact_assessment

¹⁴⁷ Wright, David, Kush Wadhwa, Paul de Hert, Dariusz Kloza “PIAF: A Privacy Impact Assessment Framework for data protection and privacy rights - Deliverable D1” *Deliverable D1 of the PIAF project*, 21 September 2011. http://www.piafproject.eu/ref/PIAF_D1_21_Sept2011Revlogo.pdf

transparency of who conducted the assessment, as well as problems (among others) relating to its transparency and attention to the legal assessment side of completing a PIA (e.g., the PIA report did not contain any reference to the New Zealand Privacy Act). Such an example demonstrates that whilst a PIA is an effective way of ensuring compliance, it is not without its own difficulties and that indeed, good practices and guidance should be followed when completing a PIA.

As will be further discussed in Section 3.1.7, ensuring anonymity is a key means of ensuring the privacy of individuals is upheld. An example of the promotion of the ethical stance towards ensuring that adequate attention is given to the privacy of data, particularly in the case of re-sharing can be seen in the Big Boulder Initiative, a trade organisations focusing on the best use of social data in businesses and organisations. They argue that it is necessary to consider the wider context of the information being circulated, and where necessary to consider whether measures should be taken to protect the privacy of others when re-sharing, for instance by ‘broadcasting a tweet without attribution or with the blurring of the name’.¹⁴⁸ Such, measures would have been particularly useful following the shooting down of Flight MH17. As argued by Watson et al., the mass sharing of an image taken by a passenger and posted on Facebook prior to boarding the flight could have been done in a manner in which the privacy of the individual was protected.¹⁴⁹

Whilst data protection appears to be a concern for some larger organisations involved in the use of social media as part of their work, this is not always the case. For instance, following the Joplin tornado in 2011, Williams et al. were successful in utilising social media, particularly the Facebook page “Joplin Tornado Info” for search and rescue efforts, and have since published a guide for others to use in implementing their own strategy in the optimum use of social media in crisis management. This guide provides useful information relating to best practices and tools to be used (for instance), but does not include any discussion or mention of privacy or data protection considerations.¹⁵⁰

There are some groups who are developing tools and technologies to help provide users with some control (in addition to privacy settings) over the availability of the information they share via their social networking sites. For instance Meier and PopRock Fellows (PopTech & Rockefeller Foundation) are currently considering the use of a no share principle with regards to the posting of tweets to help promote ethical community resilience to crises. The idea of the no share principle is for users to use a hashtag; #noshare or #ns with any material they share in a crisis so as to label it as being something they wish not to be collected, thus promoting a “new norm: avoid it being the right to be social without being sensed or exploited without our knowledge or consent”.¹⁵¹ Meier also refers to the use of tools such as TwitterSpirit and Efemr to reduce the amount of time a tweet will be made publicly available, which could be particularly useful to the protection of sensitive data by providing users with

¹⁴⁸ Big Boulder Initiative, “A code of ethics for social data: we need your help!”, 2014.

<http://blog.bigboulderinitiative.org/2014/06/05/a-code-of-ethics-for-social-data-we-need-your-help/>

¹⁴⁹ Watson, Hayley, Caroline Rizza, Martina Comes, Vitaveska Lanfranchi and Kush Wadhwa, “Flight MH17: Considerations for Social Sharing and Reporting in an Emergency”, *Emergency Management Magazine Online*, 8 September 2014. <http://www.emergencymgmt.com/training/Flight-MH17-Considerations-Social-Sharing-Reporting.html>

¹⁵⁰ Williams, Rebecca, Genevieve Williams and David Burton, “The Use of Social Media for Disaster Recovery”, *University of Missouri Extension*, 24 May 2013. [p. 20].

<http://extension.missouri.edu/greene/documents/PlansReports/using%20social%20media%20in%20disasters.pdf>

¹⁵¹ Meier, Patrick, “#NoShare: A Personal Twist on Data Privacy”, *iRevolution blog*, 15 September 2013. <http://irevolution.net/2013/09/15/noshare-hashtag/>

some control over their data.¹⁵² Such a consideration will be further examined in Section 3.2.1.

Integrating privacy considerations into the forefront of the design and subsequent use of new media applications, including social media for crisis management purposes may benefit from employing the principle “privacy by Design” (PbD). PbD is considered by the European Data Protection Supervisor, Peter Hustinx as an essential principle for enhancing citizen’s trust of ICT, where trust and privacy are interlinked.¹⁵³ Simply put, as coined in the mid-nineties by Ann Cavoukian, the Information and Privacy Commissioner of Ontario, Canada, PbD involves “the philosophy and approach of embedding privacy directly into the design and operating specifications of information technologies and systems”.¹⁵⁴ Such a philosophy involves a series of considerations, but crucially, those systematically implementing PbD must recognise the “value and benefits of adopting good privacy practices”.¹⁵⁵ An article by Rubinstein¹⁵⁶ that explores privacy by design, specifically how regulators might achieve better success in promoting the use of privacy by design, provides a preliminary list of best practices in privacy design¹⁵⁷ (based on US FTC enforcement cases and the Staff Report). In addition, as suggested by Toby Stevens of the Enterprise Privacy Group, a successful PbD approach depends upon breaking down existing barriers such as:¹⁵⁸

- poor executive awareness and a failure to recognise privacy duties at the highest levels,
- lack of consideration for privacy needs throughout the systems lifecycle
- conflicting pressures between privacy and data sharing within and outside of organisations
- lack of internationally recognised privacy management standards
- poor understanding and adoption of PETs, and
- need for a stronger, better funded ICO.

¹⁵² Meier, Patrick, “Data Protection: This Tweet Will Self-Destruct In...”, *iRevolution blog*, 6 September 2013. <http://irevolution.net/2013/09/06/this-tweet-will-self-destruct/>

¹⁵³ Cavoukian, Ann., “Privacy by Design: Origins, Meaning, and Prospects for Assuring Privacy and Trust in the Information Era”, in Yee, George O.M., ed. *Privacy Protection Measures and Technologies in Business Organizations: Aspects and Standards*. IGI Global, 2011pp. 170-208.

¹⁵⁴ Ibid., p. 173.

¹⁵⁵ Ibid. [Note: further information relating to the principles of privacy by design including the need for privacy enhancing technologies can be found in the full chapter by Cavoukian].

¹⁵⁶ Rubinstein, Ira S., “Regulating Privacy by Design”, *Berkeley Technology Law Journal*, Vol. 26, 2011, pp. 1409-1456. [p. 1454]

¹⁵⁷ Rubinstein states: This preliminary listing of privacy design practices is premised entirely on a subset of FTC enforcement cases and the views stated in the Staff Report. It is therefore a work in progress and necessarily incomplete in its current form. For alternative lists of privacy best practices, see Privacy and Security | Privacy Overview, ACM US PUB. POLICY COUNCIL, <http://us.acm.acm.org/privsec/category.cfm?cat=7&Privacy%20and%20Security> (describing 24 recommended practices for developing systems that utilise PII); Marilyn Prosch, Protecting Personal Information Using Generally Accepted Privacy Principles (GAPP) and Continuous Control Monitoring To Enhance Corporate Governance, 5 INT’L J. DISCLOSURE & GOVERNANCE 153 (2008) (describing the development of a privacy framework that resulted in the formulation of the GAPP, which consists in 10 privacy principles and 66 auditable criteria).

¹⁵⁸ Stevens, Toby, “The Privacy by Design Report”, Enterprise Privacy Group. http://ico.org.uk/~media/documents/library/data_protection/detailed_specialist_guides/pbd_presentation_2%20toby_stevens_pbd_report.ashx

Furthermore, as examined by Büscher et al. as part of their work in the EU project “Bridging Resources and Agencies in Large-Scale Emergency Management” (BRIDGE), despite engineers involved in designing tools being somewhat distant from the effects of their work, there is a history of the awareness of developers ‘responsibility to society’.¹⁵⁹ Furthermore, as they examined, a number of codes of conduct exist within computer science, to ensure an ethical stance towards the development of systems, and thus emphasis on ethical design. However, as aptly identified by the authors, whilst systems may be designed in an ethical manner that is not to say that this automatically follows through to use. Consequently, as argued by Büscher et al. “Computer professionals cannot effectively address ethical principles alone. They must be supported by society and individual users of technology, who should carry more responsibility for the beneficence/non-maleficence of IT”.¹⁶⁰

Data protection challenges are also present for those commercial organisations that may wish to re-use data they obtain via social networking websites in the aftermath of their interaction with others. For instance, as examined by Watson and Finn, the use of Twitter by some airlines following the travel chaos caused by the eruption of the Eyjafjallajökull volcano in 2010 caused potential data protection and privacy concerns particularly with regards to the profiling of customers:

“Companies such as Qantas use their social media platform to collect and use personal information about consumers to create user profiles and carry out advertising in the future (Andrejevic, 2012)¹⁶¹. Second, those relying on Twitter, Facebook or other social media feeds to gather information or solve problems may have had little opportunity to refuse consent for these types of information collection practices without putting themselves at an information disadvantage within a situation in which this information is both reliable and essential. This is indicative of a gradual undermining of consumer consent through the removal of meaningful alternatives, particularly when users are in a vulnerable situation such as in a crisis.”¹⁶²

As argued by King and Jessen, behavioural advertising techniques include the use of profiling to produce “targeted advertising to consumers”.¹⁶³ The extensive use of the web for browsing and shopping, combined with the use of location tracking technologies (such as that included in mobile phones) makes consumer profiling that much simpler, which subsequently have implications for data protection.^{164,165} When bringing this back to crisis management, it is essential that those *other* groups involved in responding to a crisis (e.g., critical infrastructure providers) take steps to ensure that those they interact with are aware of their commercial data policies, including the use of customer data for industry purposes.

¹⁵⁹ Büscher, Monika, Michael Liegl and Peter Wahlgreen, “Ethical, Legal and Social Issues: Current Practices in Multi Agency Emergency Collaboration”, *Deliverable 12.2 of the BRIDGE project*, 2014.

¹⁶⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 56.

¹⁶¹ Andrejevic, M. “Exploitation in the data mine”, in Fuchs, C., Boersma, K., Anders, A. and Sandoval, M. (eds.), *Internet and Surveillance: The Challenges of Web 2.0 and Social Media*, Routledge, London, 71-88, 2012

¹⁶² Watson and Finn, 2013, p. 4.

¹⁶³ King, N.J., Jessen, P. W., “Profiling the mobile customer – Privacy concerns when behavioural advertisers target mobile phones”, Part I, *Comput. Law and Secur. Rev.*, 2010

¹⁶⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁶⁵ The proposed update to the EU Data Protection Directive indicates that individuals have a right not to be subject to decisions based on profiling (Art. 20).

“REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation)”, *European Commission*, COM(2012) 11 final, 25 January 2012.

Consequently, as briefly examined in this sub-section, it is essential that stakeholders consider the various data protection and privacy implications of their interactions and collection of data from others in the event of a crisis.

3.1.3 Adhering to the key principles of EU data protection law

At the core of Directive 95/46/EC is the “effective protection of the fundamental right of individuals to data protection”.¹⁶⁶ The key principles of European data protection law are set out in Article 6 of the Directive and are as follows:

- i. Lawful processing: Article 6 (1) (a) and (b)
- ii. Purpose specification and limitation: Article 6 (1) (b)
- iii. Data quality principles:
 - relevancy of data; Article 6 (1) (c)
 - data accuracy: Article 6 (1) (d)
 - limited retention: Article 6 (1) (e)
- iv. Exemption for scientific research and statistics: Article 6 (1) €
- v. Fair processing: Article 6 (1) (a)
- vi. Accountability: Article 6 (2)

Though the framework of the Directive is dated as it does not adequately consider important developments since 1995, including the ever-expanding impact of globalisation and enhanced technologies surpassing global boundaries, such as social networking websites, on 25 January 2012 the European Commission proposed a data protection reform package consisting of a proposal for a General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)¹⁶⁷ meant to replace the Data Protection Directive, as well as a new General Data Protection Directive which shall provide for data protection in the areas of police and judicial cooperation in criminal matters. Ultimately the “new” Regulation aims to “strengthen online privacy rights and boost Europe's digital economy”.¹⁶⁸ Proposed changes focus on:

“reinforcing individuals' rights, strengthening the EU internal market, ensuring a high level of data protection in all areas (including police and criminal justice cooperation) ensuring proper enforcement of the rules, facilitating international transfers of personal data and setting global data protection standards. The proposed changes will give people more control over their personal data and make it easier to access it. They are designed to make sure that people's personal information is protected – no matter where it is sent, processed or stored – even outside the EU, as may often be the case on the Internet”.¹⁶⁹

More specifically and relevant to the collection of personal data within crisis management, the GDPR has strengthened its position on consent to say that it needs to be “explicit” (Art. 4 (8)). Furthermore, Art. 55. of the GDPR provides for derogations, for instance in case of

¹⁶⁶ “Why do we need an EU data protection reform?”, *European Commission*, 2012.

http://ec.europa.eu/justice/data-protection/document/review2012/factsheets/1_en.pdf

¹⁶⁷ “REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation)”, *European Commission*, COM(2012) 11 final, 25 January 2012. Note further developments: http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-14-186_en.htm

¹⁶⁸ “Commission proposes a comprehensive reform of the data protection rules”, *European Commission, Justice, Data protection, Newsroom*, 25 January 2012. http://ec.europa.eu/justice/newsroom/data-protection/news/120125_en.htm

¹⁶⁹ “Data protection reform: Frequently asked questions”, *European Commission MEMO/12/41*, 25 January 2012. http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-12-41_en.htm?locale=en

informed consent, on “important grounds of public interest”, and for the purpose of legitimate interests which “cannot be qualified as frequent or massive””, implying that consent can be undermined for situations such as crises.¹⁷⁰ Another notable point of interest is the clarification of the position on the principle of “data minimisation” (Art 5.).

The intended amendments to the EU framework should be considered by those participating in the use of social media for crisis management within the EU as well as those outside, as this (future) Directive will impact stakeholders across the globe. Such a sentiment is emphasised by the ICRC in their guidance document for humanitarian and human rights actors; “Professional standards for Protection Work”, where they argue that, “Protection actors must collect and handle information containing personal details in accordance with the rules and principles of international law and other relevant regional or national laws on individual data protection”.¹⁷¹

As systems and technologies develop, the relationship between social media, crisis management and privacy might change. For this purpose it might be relevant for those involved in crisis management to keep abreast of the latest developments in privacy and data protection expectations and laws. Within Europe, this could be achieved by liaising with the European Data Protection Supervisor¹⁷² or the national data protection authorities (DPAs) who can provide excellent guidance on how to comply with data protection (and freedom of information) obligations.¹⁷³ DPAs not only supervise legal compliance of data protection within a country, consider complaints and issue decisions, but also can work with organisations to improve their data protection practices through audits, arranging advisory visits, self-assessment questionnaires and data protection workshops. Some DPAs such as the UK ICO,¹⁷⁴ French CNIL¹⁷⁵ have a wealth of resources for different types of organisations and sectors on its website.

Legal principles aside, we next consider specifically the challenges of **informed consent, transparency, proportionality and legitimate purpose**, which have important implications for data protection, as well as other privacy, related challenges within the use of new media applications, including social media, in crisis management activities.

3.1.4 Informed consent

The use of social media in crisis situations should also consider, where it involves the collection, aggregation and use of personal data (whether actively or passively), that it ensures informed consent rules are respected and adequate measures are put in place to support this. As will be further discussed in Section 3.2.1, collecting personal data without informed consent may have serious unintended consequences, particularly when the data is brought together with other kinds of personally identifying data sets.

¹⁷⁰ Hornung, Gerrit, “A General Data Protection Regulation for Europe? Light and shade in the Commission’s draft of 25 January 2012”. *SCRIPTed*, Vol. 9, No. 1, 2012, pp. 64–81. [p. 70]

¹⁷¹ ICRC, 2013, p. 85.

¹⁷² The EDPS is independent supervisory authority devoted to protecting personal data and privacy and promoting good practice in the EU institutions and bodies by: monitoring the EU administration’s processing of personal data, advising on policies and legislation that affect privacy; and cooperating with similar authorities to ensure consistent data protection. <https://secure.edps.europa.eu/EDPSWEB/edps/EDPS>

¹⁷³ For instance see CNIL, Guide: Security of Personal Data, 2010.

http://www.cnil.fr/fileadmin/documents/en/Guide_Security_of_Personal_Data-2010.pdf

¹⁷⁴ ICO, *Sector guides*, no date. http://ico.org.uk/for_organisations/sector_guides

¹⁷⁵ CNIL, no date. <http://www.cnil.fr/>

Opinion 15/2011 of the Article 29 Data Protection Working Party elaborates the definition of consent¹⁷⁶ and reiterates that if consent is correctly used, consent is a tool giving the data subject control over the processing of his data. If incorrectly used, the data subject's control becomes illusory and consent constitutes an inappropriate basis for processing. According to the Handbook on EU Data Protection law,¹⁷⁷ to summarise:

- Consent as a legal basis for processing personal data must be free, informed and specific
- Consent must have been given unambiguously. Consent may either be given explicitly or implied by acting in a way which leaves no doubt that the data subject agrees to the processing of his or her data.
- Processing sensitive data on the basis of consent requires explicit consent.
- Consent can be withdrawn at any time

As identified in their protocol, the ICRC argue that: “Protection actors must integrate the notion of informed consent when calling upon the general public, or members of a community, to spontaneously send them information through SMS, an open Internet platform, or any other means of communication, or when using information already available on the Internet.”¹⁷⁸

However, consent is not the only basis for the legitimate processing of personal data. Article 7 (b) of the Data Protection Directive suggests data may be legitimately processed if it is “necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party”. Yet another criterion that legitimises data processing is if “it is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject”.¹⁷⁹ This criterion refers to private sector data controllers obliged by law to process data about others. Further, Article 7 (d) of the Data Protection Directive provides that personal data processing may be lawful if “it is necessary in order to protect the vital interests of the data subject”. This is related to the survival of the data subject and forms the basis for legitimate use of health data or data about missing persons. Personal data may also be lawfully processed if it is necessary to do so in the public interest and in exercise of official authority.¹⁸⁰ The legitimate interests pursued by the controller or any third party to whom the data are disclosed may provide another ground for lawful processing of data.¹⁸¹

3.1.5 Transparency

Generally speaking the term transparency refers to something that is easy to see through, it is clear and explicit. In EU data protection law, the principle of transparency establishes an obligation for the controller to keep the data subjects informed about how their data are being

¹⁷⁶ European Commission, “Opinion 15/2011 on the definition of consent”, Article 29 data protection working party, 01197/11/EN WP187, 13 July 2011. http://ec.europa.eu/justice/data-protection/article-29/documentation/opinion-recommendation/files/2011/wp187_en.pdf

¹⁷⁷ European Agency for Fundamental Rights, *Handbook on European data protection law*, Publications office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2014, p 55. http://www.echr.coe.int/Documents/Handbook_data_protection_ENG.pdf

¹⁷⁸ ICRC, 2013, p. 95.

¹⁷⁹ Article 7 (c) of the Data Protection Directive.

¹⁸⁰ Article 7 (e) of the Data Protection Directive.

¹⁸¹ Article 7 (f) of the Data Protection Directive.

used. Processing operations must be explained to the data subjects in an easily accessible way which ensures that they understand what will happen to their data. A data subject also has the right to be told by a controller on request if his or her data are being processed, and, if so, which ones.

In relation to privacy issues such as data protection, transparency is fundamental to the various activities involved in using social media in crisis management. For instance, there is a need for transparency when requesting information from the public via a social networking site such as Twitter. As revealed in D2.2 of the COSMIC project, following events such as the 2013 Boston attacks, it may be the case that the police require information from the public for investigative purposes. Similarly, following a natural disaster such as witnessed during Hurricane Sandy in 2012, in their attempts to respond to social media messages, the New York Fire Department made requests for further information.¹⁸² Accordingly, when requesting information from the public it is necessary for authorities to ensure that they inform those engaging with them via social networking websites what their policies contain information relating to organisations ensuring the protection of their data as well as any other intended secondary uses of material. The ICRC recommends that stakeholders should “...establish formal procedures on the information handling process, from collection to exchange and archiving or destruction”.¹⁸³ By promoting good practices in the ethical and legal handling of user data, organisations will be able to help build a trusting relationship with their audiences, and subsequently, ensure the better two-way engagement with social media. Thus ensuring transparency via the inclusion of publicly available data handling policies is an ethical and legal requirement for stakeholders engaging with social media as part of their crisis management activities.

Those organisations that use their own blog-based forms of communication, where visitors may be able to respond to posts with comments, should also be transparent in their (potential) subsequent use of information they may receive.¹⁸⁴ In addition, they should be transparent about any policies (e.g., participation rules) they may have relating to monitoring and editorial actions relevant to participation areas on their sites.¹⁸⁵ To illustrate, the American Red Cross have the following, “lawyer-approved” comment policy:

Remember, we encourage you to participate in this blog via comments. All viewpoints are welcome, but please be constructive. We reserve the right to make editorial decisions regarding submitted comments, including but not limited to removal of comments. The comments are moderated, so you may have to be a tiny bit patient in waiting to see them. We will review and post them as promptly as possible during regular business hours (Monday through Friday, 8:30 - 5:30).¹⁸⁶

As part of an organisation’s efforts to be transparent in their activities involving the use of social media prior to, during and after a crisis, it is essential that organisations pay attention to

¹⁸² Papadimitriou, Alex, Angelos Yannopoulos, Ioannis Kotsiopoulos, Rachel L. Finn, Hayley Watson, Kush Wadhwa and Lemi Baruh, “Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations”, *Deliverable 2.2 of the COSMIC project*, 30 September 2013.

¹⁸³ ICRC, 2013, p. 100.

¹⁸⁴ Rive, G., Hare, J., Thomas, J. and Nankivell, K. “Social Media in an Emergency: A Best Practice Guide”, Wellington Region CDEM Group: Wellington, 2012. <http://www.gw.govt.nz/assets/Emergencies--Hazards/WREMO/Publications/Social-media-in-an-emergency-A-best-practice-guide-2012.pdf> [p. 20]

¹⁸⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 20.

¹⁸⁶ American Red Cross, “About”, *American Red Cross Blog*, no date. <http://redcrosschat.org/about/#sthash.E1Jesv5Q.dpbs>

copyright and other intellectual property issues. Copyright protects original work and stops others from using it without the creator’s permission. Copyright subsists in: original literary, dramatic, musical and artistic work, including illustration and photography; original non-literary written work, e.g., software, web content and databases; sound and music recordings; film and television recordings; broadcasts and the layout of published editions of written, dramatic and musical works.¹⁸⁷ Thus, copyright protects images, website content, reports, video recordings etc.¹⁸⁸ As argued by Rive et al., it is essential that organisations avoid breaching copyright, and accordingly, when passing on information via a social media application such as Facebook or Twitter, they should ensure they provide some form of citation to demonstrate where the information they are sharing comes from. As recommended by Rive et al., being transparent in the sharing rather than copying of information is crucial, and is one legal means with which breaches of copyright can be avoided.¹⁸⁹ Similarly, for an organisation sharing their own material, it may be advisable¹⁹⁰ for them to place their own work under a copyright license such as a creative commons license, which gives “everyone from individual creators to large companies and institutions a simple, standardised way to grant copyright permissions to their creative work”.¹⁹¹ Attention to ownership can serve to complement the development of trusting and mutually beneficial relationships between crisis managers and the public.

3.1.6 Proportionality & legitimate purpose

As identified by Jones and Tahri in their review of EU data protection rules on use of data collected online, the principle of proportionality in relation to online content refers to website operators avoiding “processing excessive, irrelevant or inadequate personal data (given the purposes for which the data were collected and are used”.¹⁹² The purpose of the data minimisation principle is to ensure that only the minimum amount of data required is collected. Proportionality is also linked to transparency, in that operators should ensure they inform users if they are to use personal data for anything other than what the data was initially collected for.¹⁹³ When consent is not able to be collected, data controllers must rely on “legitimate interests”, which can be used in some EU Member States to justify data processing.¹⁹⁴

The consideration of data protection principles such as transparency, proportionality and legitimate purpose are extensive challenges to be acknowledged and responded to by those engaging with the use of social media as part of their crisis management activities. As argued by Palen et al. it is necessary for researchers and stakeholders directly involved in utilising ICT for crisis response purposes to consider how their practices lie within the laws, policies and regulations.¹⁹⁵

¹⁸⁷ Intellectual Property Office, “How copyright protects your work”. <https://www.gov.uk/copyright/overview>

¹⁸⁸ “Copyright”, *Intellectual Property Office*, 30 November 2008. <http://www.ipso.gov.uk/copy.htm>

¹⁸⁹ Rive et al., 2012, p. 19.

¹⁹⁰ Ibid.

¹⁹¹ “Creative commons: about the licenses”, *Creative Commons*, no date. <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/>

¹⁹² Jones, Richard, and Dalal Tahri, “An overview of EU data protection rules on use of data collected online”, *Computer law & security review*, Vol. 27, 2011, pp. 630-636. [p. 633].

¹⁹³ Jones and Tahri, 2011, p. 633.

¹⁹⁴ Ibid., p. 632.

¹⁹⁵ Palen, Leysia, Kenneth M. Anderson, Gloria Mark, James Martin, Douglas Sicker, Martha Palmer and Dirk Grunwald, “A Vision for Technology-mediated Support for Public Participation & Assistance in Mass Emergencies & Disasters.” *Proceedings of the 2010 ACM-BCS Visions of Computer Science Conference*, ACM-BCS, 2010, Swinton, UK, pp. 1-12. <http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=1811182.1811194>

3.1.7 Anonymity

An important privacy related consideration with regards to the use of social media in crisis management is upholding the ethical principle of maintaining an individual’s anonymity. Anonymisation (and pseudonymisation) are safeguards or means of minimising the risks of misusing personal data and might be an additional legal obligation before secondary or any re-use of data. As argued by Rive et al. it is essential that those organisations involved in sharing material such as photos of disaster sites, take the appropriate measures to ensure the privacy of individuals is upheld (e.g., masking faces and vehicle number plates).¹⁹⁶ Furthermore, as suggested by the American Red Cross, it is essential that appropriate permission is gained from people/clients to ensure their privacy is respected.¹⁹⁷

A report on *Research using Social Media: Users’ Views* by the National Centre for Social Research (UK) graphically illustrates reasons for and against observing informed consent and anonymity:¹⁹⁸

Figure 4: For and against informed consent and anonymity

The issue of remaining anonymous is also relevant to those members of the public, including citizen journalists, who are actively involved in sharing information with others, including authorities and CSO’s. Whilst an individual may choose to utilise certain privacy restrictive settings on their social networking sites or blogs, that is not to say that the information they do

¹⁹⁶ Rive et al., 2012, p. 19.
¹⁹⁷ American Red Cross, “Social Media Handbook for Red Cross Field Units”, *American Red Cross, Slideshare*, 17 July 2009. <http://www.slideshare.net/wharman/social-media-handbook-for-red-cross-field-units>, slide 87.
¹⁹⁸ Beninger, Kelsey, Alexandra Fry, Natalie Jago, Hayley Lepps, Laura Nass and Hannah Silvester, *Research using Social Media: Users’ Views*, NatCen Social Research, 20 Feb 2014. <http://www.natcen.ac.uk/media/282288/p0639-research-using-social-media-report-final-190214.pdf>

publicly reveal about themselves will not inadvertently reveal important information about their identity.¹⁹⁹ This can be attributed to the challenge of dealing with “weak identifiers”, that is “pieces of information that can be used to identify individual users”.²⁰⁰ As illustrated by Palen et al. there are a range of techniques that can be used to remove weak identifiers, however, they argue that within crisis management, it may be more effective to “allow users to have a high degree of control and flexibility with respect to the types of personally identifying information revealed”, and thus communication and transparency is required in obtaining consent.²⁰¹ As will be seen in the subsequent section, the difficulty of remaining anonymous and safeguarding an individual’s anonymity is of particular importance to ensuring a persons’ security.

Ensuring anonymity during a crisis is one challenge, a second challenge is ensuring that a person’s data remains anonymous when organisations and third parties (e.g., researchers) utilise information shared during a crisis to further understand the crisis at a later date (i.e., for research purposes). This is of particularly importance when terms and conditions from some social networking sites, e.g., Twitter, emphasise the “re-use” of data.²⁰² For instance, in their study of the use of Twitter by the London Metropolitan Police and Manchester Police following the 2011 summer riots in the UK, Bartlett and Miller took measures to ensure that they upheld ethical principles of ensuring anonymity:

“...we carefully reviewed all tweets selected for quotation in this report and considered whether the publication of the tweet, and the links, pictures and quotations contained within, might result in any harm, distress, to the originator or other parties involved. For example, if any possibly invasive personal information were revealed in the body of the tweet, this was not used. As a further measure, we removed any user names; and in a small number of cases, ‘cloaked’ the text so it could not allow for the identification of the originator”.²⁰³

Thus ensuring anonymity should be an important consideration in the ethical re-use of other people’s data.

3.1.8 Increasing surveillance

As discussed in Deliverables 2.1 and 2.2 of the COSMIC project, the use of GPS based services integrated into new media applications including, Facebook, Twitter, Google Maps etc., mean that individuals provide others with access to their personal data regarding their location, which may contribute to responders abilities to manage a crisis, particularly in locating individuals.^{204,205} To illustrate, following their study of the disruption caused by the ash cloud stemming from the Eyjafjallajokull volcano in 2010, Reuter et al., advocated the use of tagging and geo-tagging of social network based content (e.g., the sharing of photographs and messages on Twitter), to help crisis managers determine the precise location

¹⁹⁹ Yates et al., 2009, p. 6.

²⁰⁰ Palen et al., 2010, p. 9.

²⁰¹ Ibid.

²⁰² Bartlett, Jamie, and Carl Miller, “@metpoliceuk how twitter is changing modern policing: the case of the Woolwich aftermath”, *DEMOS*, 19 June 2013. [p. 5]

²⁰³ Ibid., 2013, p. 6.

²⁰⁴ Watson, Hayley, Rachel L. Finn, Kush Wadhwa and Angelos Yannopoulos, “State of the art of communication technology for crisis management: Baseline analysis of communication technologies and their applications”, *Deliverable 2.1 of the COSMIC project*, 31 August 2013.

²⁰⁵ Papadimitriou et al., 2013.

of an incident.²⁰⁶ However, as identified by Watson and Finn, such practices have the potential to affect an individual's privacy of location²⁰⁷, and therefore require clear policies from authorities regarding the secondary use of the data they collect and receive via their interactions with social media; once again transparency is crucial.

Data retention for secondary use following a crisis can also be seen to be problematic in terms of threatening a person's privacy when personal data is collected and stored for intelligence purposes, thereby being a form of surveillance; data surveillance, otherwise referred to as dataveillance. As identified by Clark, dataveillance involves "the systematic use of personal data systems in the investigation or monitoring of the actions or communications of one or more persons".²⁰⁸ The expanse of digital technology and the ever-growing emphasis on the use of big data for analytics means that the collection and examination of personal data for monitoring is becoming more common place and promoted as a tool for investigative purposes, including disaster response activities.²⁰⁹ Dataveillance greatly impacts Finn et al's "privacy of data and image" which "includes concerns about making sure that individuals' data is not automatically available to other individuals and organisations and that people can "exercise a substantial degree of control over that data and its use".²¹⁰

In relation to crisis management, dataveillance raises particular challenges relating to privacy and surveillance and the monitoring of social media. As argued by McCarthy and Yates, "others fear that government agencies involved in disaster response might track, catalogue, or otherwise invade the privacy of public individuals who do decide to help".²¹¹ Similarly, as identified by Lindsay, in the US, concerns relating to the collection, retention and data mining of personal information by the federal government for disaster recovery purposes is seen as a threat as it may be used for investigative purposes; "would the federal government compile records after a terrorist attack to help investigate certain individuals?"²¹² As identified in D2.2 of the COSMIC project, during the Boston marathon attacks in 2013 this could have been problematic, not only as authorities, including the Boston police, had asked for members of the public to submit photographs to them to help with the investigation, but furthermore, as will be seen in the next section, the use of data for surveillance purposes can also lend itself to security issues relating to digital volunteerism and the miss-labelling of individuals for investigation purposes.²¹³ A report by the "Increasing Resilience in Surveillance Societies" (IRISS) project, that examined the Boston bombing as a case study, highlights the problem of data analysis following an overload of visual images and intelligence data.²¹⁴ It highlights how "controlling the use of data can be a problem. Rumours spreading uncontrolled through

²⁰⁶ Reuter, Christian, Alexandra Marc and Volkmar Pipek, "Social Software as an Infrastructure for Crisis Management - a Case Study About Current Practice and Potential Usage". *Proceedings of the 8th International ISCRAM Conference*, Lisbon, Portugal, 2011.

²⁰⁷ Finn et al., 2013.

²⁰⁸ Roger Clarke, "Introduction to Dataveillance and Information Privacy, and Definitions of Terms", *Xamax Consultancy*, Aug 1997. <http://www.rogerclarke.com/DV/Intro.html>

²⁰⁹ Almon, Gabriele, "The Conversation About Big Data in Crisis/Disaster Response Is Happening Now." *Tech 4 Relief*, 27 June 2013. <http://www.tech4relief.com/2013/06/27/the-conversation-about-big-data-in-crisisdisaster-response-is-happening-now/>

²¹⁰ Finn et al., 2013, p. 8.

²¹¹ Yates and Paquette, 2010, p. 12.

²¹² Lindsay, 2011, p. 7.

²¹³ Papadimitriou et al., 2013.

²¹⁴ Kreissl, Reinhard, "The Boston bombing", *Deliverable D6.1 – A report on resilience in "democratic" surveillance societies*, The IRISS Consortium, p. 126. <http://irissproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2014/06/D6.1-Resilience-report.pdf>

the social media can create a dangerous situation of vigilantism that might affect innocent persons.”²¹⁵

Bartlett and Miller have examined the use of social media for intelligence (SOCMINT) purposes in their study of the use of Twitter by the London Metropolitan police during the Woolwich attacks in 2013, where they found both opportunities and challenges for policing with regards to the use of social media. A crucial challenge they identified includes:

“...there are legal and ethical questions – still open – as to how the police can collect and use social media information in a way that is proportionate, legal and can command public confidence and support. The official collection and use of social media information is a controversial and contested practice, especially for the purposes of intelligence and security”.²¹⁶

In Europe this is of particular importance. As examined by the EU project COMPOSITE in their study of police officers attitudes to the use of social media in policing, social media was seen to have a “perceived value” in that it had the potential to be used for a range of services including: notifying disaster-related issues, notifying crime problems, public relations, intelligence, listening/monitoring etc.²¹⁷ However, as discussed elsewhere in the COSMIC project, including D2.3²¹⁸ and D4.2, although data mining for intelligence purposes may present an opportunity for policing and other response agencies, there is also the possibility that it could result in a heightened sense of fear on behalf of those ordinarily using social media.²¹⁹ Heightened surveillance, could for some, particularly those ruled by authoritarian regimes, could result in them feeling as though their civil liberties are threatened, particularly with regards to ‘the free flow of information’²²⁰, leading to self-censorship on part of individuals. Such an activity would go against, efforts that are being made to build relationships with those using social media to enhance communication. Consequently, whilst intelligence is important, where necessary, transparency is essential in maintaining trust.

A second form of surveillance to consider in relation to the use of social media within crisis management is that of counter-surveillance. Monahan defines counter-surveillance as; “intentional, tactical uses, or disruptions of surveillance technologies to challenge institutional power asymmetries”.²²¹ Here, counter-surveillance can be seen as an opportunity for those who may be oppressed. As discussed in D4.2 of the COSMIC project, when considering political crises, individuals under control by others are able to use new media to counter the surveillance that they themselves are exposed to.²²² Baruh et al., provide the example of counter-surveillance following the protests in Egypt in 2011, where there was not only evidence of counter-surveillance by the public, but also the opportunity for activists and developers to work together to combat the situation they were facing.²²³

²¹⁵ Ibid.

²¹⁶ Bartlett and Miller, 2013, p. 17.

²¹⁷ Bayerl, Saskia P., “Social Media Study in European Police Forces: First Results on Usage and Acceptance”, *Preliminary report from the COMPOSITE project*, 29 September 2012. [p. 12]

²¹⁸ Scifo, Salvatore and Lemi Baruh, Report on the adverse use and reliability of new media, *Deliverable 2.3 of the COSMIC project*, 30 November 2013.

²¹⁹ Baruh, Lemi, Hayley Watson, Kim Hagen, Kush Wadhwa, Zeynep Günel, Haluk Mert Bal, Salvatore Scifo, and Yusuf Salman, “Report on Citizen Involvement and Ethics”, *Deliverable 4.2 of the COSMIC project*, 2014.

²²⁰ Ibid., p. 40.

²²¹ Monahan, Torin, “Counter-Surveillance as Political Intervention?,” *Social Semiotics*, Vol. 16, No. 4, December 2006, pp. 515–534. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10350330601019769>.

²²² Baruh et al., 2014.

²²³ Ibid., p. 19.

In Egypt, Hosni Mubarak's regime took a more radical direction to suppress the uprising; in the nights of January 27 and 28, 2011, when the protests were at their peak, the government shut Internet off in order to prevent protests from spreading. "Speak to Tweet" is a service by Google that was initiated to overcome the Internet disruptions in Egypt. The service helped people to tweet without Internet connection. Activists were able to tweet by phoning certain international numbers and leaving voicemail messages. The messages were instantly tweeted with the hashtag #Egypt. Thus as a means of countering oppression, counter-surveillance through social media and new media collaboration provides an opportunity for those fighting censorship and oppression. It also presents an opportunity for the development of tools to counter challenges that some may face.

A third form of surveillance that should be considered as a potential challenge is lateral surveillance. Lateral surveillance involves peer-to-peer surveillance.²²⁴ As discussed in D2.4, whilst in some societies individuals are invited to be vigilant of what is taking place around them, particularly in their efforts to manage risks (e.g., the threat of terrorism or crime), there is the danger that this approach to enhancing security could pose a problem from a social perspective. As argued by Baruh et al.:²²⁵

More often than not, in the post-9/11 world, vigilant attention disproportionately targets certain segments of the population who are stereotypically linked to a type of criminal activity...Hence, when we consider recent examples of how both mass media and users online rushed to the misidentification of culprits in the Oklahoma Bombing, Virginia Tech Shootings and the Boston Marathon Bombing, it is plausible to expect that, even if corrected later, such (mis)information may have long term implications in terms of racial prejudice and animosity.

The inherent social nature of social media enables individuals to act as a group, and in many cases, crowdsourcing can provide an important benefit to assisting in a crisis, such as the need to monitor a health related crisis.²²⁶ However, there is a great need for consideration, on part of authorities and individuals to consider the consequences and impact of their actions in a virtual setting, particularly if those actions may prove harmful to others.

The IRISS project,²²⁷ has released a Handbook on increasing resilience in surveillance societies (as a printed publication and as an online tool)²²⁸. The handbook is aimed at different stakeholders, such as policy-makers and regulators, consultancies, service providers, the media, civil society organisations and the public to help them think about how they can increase resilience in a surveillance society, for themselves and for their fellow citizens. Resilience to surveillance requires ways of preventing, mitigating, remedying and "bouncing forward" from the negative effects of surveillance. To this effect, the Handbook

²²⁴ Andrejevic, Mark, "The Work of Watching One Another: Lateral Surveillance, Risk, and Governance," *Surveillance & Society*, Vol. 2, September 1, 2002. <http://library.queensu.ca/ojs/index.php/surveillance-and-society/article/view/3359>.

²²⁵ Baruh et al., 2014, pp. 51-53.

²²⁶ Kamel Boulos, Maged N, Bernd Resch, David N Crowley, John G Breslin, Gunho Sohn, Russ Burtner, William A Pike, Eduardo Jezierski, and Kuo-Yu Slayer Chuang, "Crowdsourcing, Citizen Sensing and Sensor Web Technologies for Public and Environmental Health Surveillance and Crisis Management: Trends, OGC Standards and Application Examples," *International Journal of Health Geographics*, Vol. 10, No. 1, January 2011, p. 67. <http://www.ij-healthgeographics.com/content/10/1/67>.

²²⁷ IRISS project website, 2014. <http://www.irissproject.eu/>

²²⁸ IRISS, *Handbook on Increasing Resilience in a Surveillance Society: Key considerations for policy-makers, regulators, consultancies, service providers, the media, civil society organisations and the public*, October 2014. http://irissproject.eu/?page_id=610

contextualises surveillance, surveillance societies and the relationship between surveillance, democracy and resilience. The Handbook sets out questions (generic and specifically addressed to target stakeholder groups) that intend to provoke consideration of a proposed or existing surveillance systems, technologies, practices or other initiatives. It also offers a list of measures that can be taken to increase resilience in surveillance societies and to restrict the scope of surveillance systems to what can be legitimately justified and to minimise the impacts of surveillance systems on the individual, groups and society. The handbook is not intended to be or replace a full-fledged surveillance impact assessment (SIA) or privacy impact assessment (PIA). However, it may stimulate awareness that an SIA and/or PIA should be undertaken. Thus, it could be a useful resource to consider for crisis management stakeholders using social media via surveillance systems and technologies, in a surveillant manner or creating security priorities during disasters.

As this sub-section has shown, issues relating to privacy and surveillance can yield both opportunities and challenges for the use of social media within crisis management. A central lesson stems from the knowledge that there is a fine line between surveillance as a force for good, and surveillance as a controlling tool. Consequently, efforts are required to consider the consequences of surveillance-based activities on others. This is particularly the case when such activities could undermine citizens' privacy and trust.²²⁹

3.2 SECURITY

Whilst the use of social media in a crisis has its benefits and presents many opportunities for enhancing situational awareness and response capabilities, there are, however, also a series of security related challenges that must be taken into consideration concerning the emphasis placed on the use of new media applications, including social media in relation to crisis management activities. Accordingly, within this sub-section, partners will explore issues relating to information security, challenges surrounding the reliability of information and the physical security of individuals involved in using social media during a crisis.

3.2.1 Protection of information from loss or theft

The challenge of ensuring and safeguarding information is of the utmost importance to the use of new media applications in crisis management activities. As argued by Dlamini et al. information security is not a new concept, rather the need to secure information is “as old as information itself”, for we have long been concerned with securing the transmittance, stored and processed.²³⁰ Dlamini et al. chart the historical background of information security citing key moments in history such as the need for encryption to secure the telegraph in the 1840's, as well as the risk posed by the remote use of data in the 1960's. As technology has progressed so too has the threats and risk we are faced with to ensure the security of information. The 21st Century is typified by a “strong dependence on IT infrastructure” which has brought with it opportunities for the “hacking community”, both in terms of providing a source of “fun” and a challenge, as well as providing a means for financial gain.²³¹ Consequently we are faced with information related threats including (but not limited to),

²²⁹ Bartlett, Jamie, Carl Miller, Jeremy Crump Lynee and Middleton, “Policing in an information age”, *DEMOS, CASM policy paper*, March 2013.

²³⁰ Dlamini, Moses T., Jan H.P. Eloff, and Mariki M. Eloff, “Information Security: The Moving Target.” *Computers & Security*, Vol. 28, No. 3–4, May 2009, pp. 189–198.

²³¹ *Ibid.*, p. 191.

identity theft, social engineering, phishing, sabotage, malware attacks etc.^{232, 233, 234} For instance, following the Boston marathon attacks in April 2013, cyber gangs used the attacks, along with a devastating explosion of a Texas fertiliser plant to conduct a phishing scam. The scam involved encouraging users to view a YouTube video of the events, which then triggered an infection in the user's computer.²³⁵ Furthermore, a 2013 overview of security threats relating to the use of social networking websites by the European Union Agency for Network and Information Security (ENISA) found that the top 10 threats included: worms/Trojans, information leakage, phishing, spam, identify theft, exploit kits (e.g., spam campaigns), physical theft/loss/damage, drive-by downloads, code injection and botnets.²³⁶ Consequently, whilst social networking may provide an opportunity for crisis management, it is not without its security challenges.

When considering information security in relation to crisis management activities, as identified by Yates et al. there is a danger that following some crises, the mining of data by some could be used for identity theft as well as other malicious activities targeted at vulnerable groups.²³⁷ As noted by Yates et al., even when personal identity information may be masked, as discussed in the previous sub-section, there is still the threat that the collection and analysis of weak identifiers could lead to uncovering a person's true identity.²³⁸ Such a threat may be particularly dangerous when considering the use of new media applications such as Facebook and Twitter in political crises.²³⁹ For instance the sharing of perspectives by citizen journalists, as well as any physical evidence (e.g., photographs, video footage etc.) that they may share, may put both themselves and others at risk in highly volatile political situations. This may be particularly troublesome if there is the potential danger of any identifiable information being shared or subsequently collected by others for intelligence purposes.

As time progresses and our understanding of the challenges relating to the safety of information advances, some developers are taking measures to enhance the safety of information shared via social media. For instance, Efemr a small start-up company, have developed an application for Twitter that enables the self-destruction of tweets. As explained by Warr writing for WIRED magazine:²⁴⁰

²³² Ibid.

²³³ Geers, Kenneth, *Strategic cyber security*, NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence, CCD COE Publication, Estonia, June 2011.

²³⁴ Martin, Nigel, John and Rice, "Cybercrime: Understanding and addressing the concerns of stakeholders", *Computers & security*, Vol. 30, 2011, pp. 803-814.

²³⁵ Acohido, Byron, "Phishing campaign leverages news of bombings, explosion", *The Last Watchdog on Internet Security [Blog]*, 19 April 2013. <http://lastwatchdog.com/phishing-campaign-leverages-news-bombings-explosion/>

²³⁶ European Union Agency for Network and Information Security, *ENISA Threat Landscape 2013: Overview of current and emerging cyber-threats*, 11 December 2013. <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/activities/risk-management/evolving-threat-environment/enisa-threat-landscape-2013-overview-of-current-and-emerging-cyber-threats>

²³⁷ Yates, David, and Scott Paquette, "Emergency Knowledge Management and Social Media Technologies: A Case Study of the 2010 Haitian Earthquake", *International Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 31, No. 1, February 2011, pp. 6–13.

²³⁸ Yates and Paquette, p. 12.

²³⁹ Palen et al., 2010, p. 8.

²⁴⁰ Warr, Philippa, "Twitter App Efemr Offers Self-Destructing Tweets," *Wired UK*, October 1, 2013. <http://www.wired.co.uk/news/archive/2013-04/29/self-destructing-tweets>.

Efemr works by connecting with your Twitter account and monitoring it for time-related hashtags. Tweets tagged #5m will disappear after 5 minutes, things marked #1h will vanish after an hour and so on.

Efemr does not simply allow individuals to control their public tweets, but also the information they share via Twitter in a private, direct manner. Such an initiative places further control in the hands of users with regards to the sharing of information. In some instances, such as the use of Twitter during a political crisis, such a mechanism could serve fruitful to ensuring individuals security. Thus, further research and development paves the way to enhancing opportunities for enhancing privacy. The extent to which social media users are aware of these types of applications is, however, unknown, and there is therefore a need for greater visibility and promotion of these privacy-enhancing tools.

In order to take measures to help ensure the safety of information, and the anonymity of a person's personal data, as identified by the ICRC, organisations should take steps to ensure that they “analyse the different potential risks linked to the collection, sharing or public display of the information and adapt the way they collect, manage and publicly release the information accordingly”.²⁴¹ Thus awareness by organisations involved in sharing information and promoting the sharing of information should acknowledge and outline the risks associated with it via new media applications, which in turn places emphasis on the need for digital literacy and a wider understanding of the various online threats. Furthermore, the need for greater understanding regarding threats to information security means greater responsibility for data security on part of the various different types of stakeholders involved in crisis management activities.

As part of the EU Directive 95/46/EC on data protection, website operatives and organisational rules require attention to data security. As identified by Jones and Tahri, whilst the Directive “does not specify what particular measures must be in place, other than that they should ensure a level of security appropriate to the nature of the data to be protected and the risks associated with unauthorised or unlawful processing and accidental loss, destruction or damage”.²⁴² Ensuring the security of information also involves the integration of data security practices such as “handling and treatment” of personal and confidential information, e.g., through limiting the collection of data with personal content, install electronic security codes of practice and monitoring physical and electronic access to sensitive information.²⁴³ Once again, in light of the threat to individuals involved in political crises that are turning to social media as an outlet for disseminating their own views and news, there is a need to ensure the physical security of information, particularly sensitive information. As outlined by the ICRC, “Security safeguards appropriate to the sensitivity of the information must be in place prior to any collection of information, to ensure protection from loss or theft, unauthorised access, disclosure, copying, use or modification, in any format in which it is kept”.²⁴⁴ At the same time it is necessary for individuals themselves to consider the potential threat to their security in sharing personal information. Consequently, nation states should, as identified by Martin and Rice, consider the need for education and awareness raising activities to help protect individuals from those threats they may have from sharing information online.²⁴⁵

²⁴¹ ICRC, 2013, p. 86.

²⁴² Jones and Tahri, 2011, p. 633.

²⁴³ Martin and Rice, 2011, p. 807.

²⁴⁴ ICRC, 2013, p. 91.

²⁴⁵ Martin and Rice, 2011.

3.2.2 Reliability of information

As will be extensively discussed in Deliverable 2.3 of the COSMIC project; “Report on the adverse use and reliability of new media”²⁴⁶, the reliability of information is indeed an important challenge to security that should be taken into consideration by those engaging with new media applications as part of their crisis management activities.

As identified by Lindsay, information that is “false, inaccurate or outdated could complicate the situational awareness of an incident and consequently hinder or slow response efforts. Inaccurate information could also jeopardise the safety of first responders and the community”.²⁴⁷ To illustrate, following wildfires in California in August 2013, authorities asked residents not to turn to social media for fire-related updates as the number of digital rumours circulating caused some individuals to feel a heightened sense of anxiety and fear (e.g., the Groveland firehouse had burned down; authorities were cutting power lines to force people to evacuate; police had arrested an arsonist who started it etc.).²⁴⁸ As Watson and Wadhwa argue, there is therefore a need for authorities to be particularly conscious of the abilities of social media to function as a rumour mill, however, there are tactics such as the adoption of verification practices and active monitoring and debunking of rumours that authorities and response organisations can employ in order to utilise the benefits afforded by social media to establish an opportunity to help quell rumours and reduce public concerns, thereby pro-actively responding to rumours.²⁴⁹

An example of industry responding to opportunities for their products in crisis management activities includes the newly launched Twitter’s alert service, where officials and NGO’s can sign up to Twitter’s Alert Service to send official alerts using a specialised Tweet composer to create a Tweet and tag it as a critical alert to be pushed to their subscribers via a notification or SMS message. Such a service may help to divert users’ attention to more “official” sources of information on social media.²⁵⁰

In addition to the spreading of false rumours, there may also be the danger of some individuals utilising other people’s social media use (including response organisations) for malicious purpose, and thus organisations should, as identified by Lindsay, “develop measures to mitigate those possibilities”.²⁵¹ As outlined by Palen et al., under cyber terrorism conditions, malicious users may deliberately contribute false or misleading information which could subsequently disrupt efforts of “self-policing and accuracy attainment”.²⁵² Accordingly, as identified by the ICRC, organisations utilising social media for managing a crisis should try to be “explicit as to the level of reliability and accuracy of information they use or

²⁴⁶ Due: November 2013.

²⁴⁷ Lindsay, Bruce R., *Social Media and Disasters: Current Uses, Future Options, and Policy Considerations*, CRS Report for Congress, Congressional Research Service, 2011.

<http://www.fas.org/sgp/crs/homsec/R41987.pdf> [p. 7]

²⁴⁸ Carroll, Rory, “California Officials Ask Residents to Avoid Social Media for Rim Fire Updates.” *The Guardian*, 27 August 2013. <http://www.theguardian.com/world/2013/aug/27/rim-fire-california-social-media-avoid>

²⁴⁹ Watson, Hayley and Kush Wadhwa, “The evolution of citizen journalism in crises: From crisis reporting to crisis management” in Thorsen, Einar and Stuart Allan (ed.) *Citizen Journalism: Global Perspectives, Volume Two*. Peter Lang, Oxford, 2014.

²⁵⁰ Twitter, “A step-by-step guide to Twitter Alerts”, *Twitter Alerts*, 2013. <https://about.twitter.com/alerts/how-it-works>

²⁵¹ Lindsay, 2011, p. 7.

²⁵² Palen et al., 2010, p. 8.

share”.²⁵³ Similarly, as argued by Humanity Road, a virtual volunteer organisation working within the domain of disaster response to inform the public on how to survive after a crisis, the use of social media, such as Twitter by volunteers should be conducted along a “do no harm” principle, for instance: “It is safer to share no news than to share inaccurate news. Rumours put lives at risk”.²⁵⁴

3.2.3 The security of the citizen

As indicated to in this chapter, whilst many opportunities can stem from the use of social media to aid crisis management, challenges relating to privacy and security can indeed have an impact on citizens, whether it be from misuse, loss or theft of their personal data, or by malicious attacks. However, it is important to consider other security related impacts on the security of the citizen. In particular, this sub-section will briefly consider those issues relating to vigilante justice and the physical safety of individuals operating in volatile areas.

As examined by Finn in Deliverable 2.2 of the COSMIC project, following the 2013 Boston marathon attacks, there was extensive evidence of the use of the social networking site, Reddit, by citizens to gather pictorial evidence (as also requested by the Boston Police) from the scene of the Boston attacks, where users were invited to share their images. This led to some individuals seeking to take efforts into their own hands, through means of lateral surveillance, to identify those responsible, leading to the wrongful identification of innocent victims. Thus, whilst in some cases, such as responding to missing airline MH370, with over two million people assisting search efforts²⁵⁵, crowdsourcing provides an opportunity for efficient contributions, in others, crowdsourcing behaviour in the face of a crisis, if unregulated, can lead to the risk of innocent individuals being inappropriately labelled and targeted as was seen following the Boston bombings (2013).²⁵⁶

Similarly, as identified by Rizza et al., vigilante justice was also present following the ice hockey Stanley Cup final series between the Vancouver Canucks and the Boston Bruins which took place in Vancouver in June 2011 leading to riots. The riots led to individuals taking it upon themselves to publicise the riots via social media, and to share information and data (upon request) with authorities of who they believed rioters to be. Furthermore, they then engaged in “do it yourself justice” by publicly damning those responsible via social networking sites, which has been labelled a form of “bad ethics” by Henry (2011).²⁵⁷ Thus, law enforcement agencies should consider the impact of requesting information and content via social media for any potential use and should subsequently take measures to ensure that they publicise how *they* will utilise the information. As identified by Rizza et al., perhaps there is a need for “authorities to establish clear rules regarding citizen cooperation in a crisis

²⁵³ ICRC, 2013, p. 89.

²⁵⁴ Starbird, Kate, and Leysia Palen, “Working & Sustaining the Virtual “Disaster Desk”, Computer Supported Cooperative Work and Social Computing (CSCW), 23-27 February 23 2013, San Antonio, Texas, USA. [p. 3].

²⁵⁵ Fishwick, Carmen, “Tomnod – the Online Search Party Looking for Malaysian Airlines Flight MH370,” *The Guardian*, 14 March 2014. <http://www.theguardian.com/world/2014/mar/14/tomnod-online-search-malaysian-airlines-flight-mh370>.

²⁵⁶ Tapia, Andrea, Nicolas LaLone and Hyun-Woo Kim, “Run Amok: Group Crowd Participation in Identifying the Bomb and Bomber from the Boston Marathon Bombing,” *Proceedings of the 11th International ISCRAM Conference*, Pennsylvania, USA, 2014.

²⁵⁷ Rizza, Caroline, Angelia G. Pereira and Paula Curvelo, ““Do-it-yourself justice”: considerations of social media use in a crisis situation: the case of the 2011 Vancouver riots”, *Proceedings of the 10th International ISCRAM Conference*, Baden-Baden, Germany, May 2013.

situation”.²⁵⁸ Similarly, there is a requirement for greater education on part of the public, to help emphasise the need for restraint in participating in targeted digital volunteerism.

Lastly, it is necessary for organisations and members of the public to consider the safety of those individuals participating in the collection of information to be shared via social media to help understand and manage a crisis. As noted by Watson, there is the risk that individuals could place themselves in danger to record information, and could subsequently need further help from authorities. Similarly, there is the ethical dilemma involved in participating in citizen journalism. As argued by Bakker and Paterson, following the 2005 London attacks, the capturing of graphic images of the attacks, particularly those affected, could be seen as a form of citizen paparazzi, where citizens’ may be more concerned with capturing a newsworthy photo, rather than staying out of the way, or in extreme cases stepping into help. Whilst these may seem like extreme cases, encouraging graphic evidence from those at the scene of a crisis, particularly by the media in their efforts to publicise an event, could place individuals in danger. Thus, it is necessary to consider the ethical dimension of citizen involvement by different stakeholders that may have an interest in participating in utilising social media to gather material from those at the scene of a crisis.²⁵⁹

3.3 SOCIAL MEDIA ACTIVISM

Use of social media by the crowds is increasingly becoming ubiquitous. Proliferation and integration of social media, most specifically social network sites and microblogging into the daily routines of individuals have allowed people to link and interact with each other without being limited by time and spatial constraints.

The aim of this section is to discuss how the increased connectivity enabled by social media may provide opportunities for social activism. Specifically, the section will review secondary data regarding recent social movements such as Occupy Wall Street, the Arab Spring, 15-M in Spain, protests in Greece, Euromaidan protests in Ukraine, and Gezi Park protests in Turkey to outline how social media facilitate mobilisation and transnational communication as well as potentially changing how activist networks organize. In the first subsection, we will outline the opportunities presented by quicker dissemination of information exchange on mobilisation of social movements. This subsection will also discuss how social movements dispersed in different geographies can influence and inspire each other. The second subsection will detail how social networks may also act in ways that influence the modus operandi of activist networks by changing the decision making mechanism and the role individual activists play in contemporary networks.

3.3.1 Mobilisation through networks

The recent growth of social media brings about important changes with respect to the power relations between mass media, which have had a monopoly over gatekeeping and sense making functions, and individuals. As Castells describes through the concept of “mass self-communication”, social network technologies allow what were formerly passive audiences to transform into active communicators.²⁶⁰ As a result of this transformation, social activists

²⁵⁸ Rizza et al., 2013, p. 6.

²⁵⁹ Watson, Hayley, “Dependent Citizen Journalism and the Publicity of Terror”, *Terrorism and Political Violence*, Vol. 24, No. 3, 2013, pp. 465-482.

²⁶⁰ Manuel Castells, *Communication and Power* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009).

have also been able to gain more control over how their ideas are presented and disseminated. This potential of networking technologies was evident in as early as 1999, during the Seattle WTO protests, when the activists utilised mobile communication technologies and the self-publishing capabilities provided by the internet to challenge the mainstream coverage of the protests.²⁶¹

As underlined by recent political unrests, particularly when faced with repressive regimes, protestors increasingly resort to social media to disseminate information in the wake of considerably biased reporting of the events by mass media. For example, as surveys conducted during the Gezi Protests (2013) in Turkey suggest, a significant majority of the protestors (84%) indicated that one of the reasons why they participated in the protests was to react to the decline media freedoms as a result of increasing government pressure and conglomeratisation of media outlets.²⁶² Likewise, in Deliverable 2.2 of the COSMIC project, we observed that reliance on mass media as a source of information declined significantly during the protests while close to 85% of the respondents reported using social media to gather information about the protests.²⁶³

The role that social media plays in dissemination of information to the large public is critical for the extent to which it can act as a catalyst for mobilisation of social movements.²⁶⁴ Manuel Castells describes this relationship between dissemination of information and mobilisation of activists by claiming that contemporary movements increasingly rely on “viral” dissemination of information.²⁶⁵ And, a number of recent events illustrate how virally diffused information, whether in the form of videos, a post on SNS networks, or a blog, may influence the extent to which a wider public will be mobilised to join a movement. For example, during the Arab Spring, a video blog (Vlog) which was posted Asma Mafhouz on her personal Facebook account in January 18, 2011, is considered to be an important catalyst for the widespread participation in the protests in Tahrir Square on January 25, 2011. Here, the dissemination of the video on YouTube played a critical role in the ability of the message to reach millions of people.²⁶⁶ Also, a YouTube video showing how Egyptian soldiers were beating a female protestor, who was later known as the “blue bra girl” provided the imagery that motivated many to participate in the protests. According to Castells, “The viral nature of these videos and the volume and speed with which news on the events in Egypt became available to the wider public in the country and in the world was key to the process of mobilisation against Mubarak”.²⁶⁷

²⁶¹ Almeida, P. D., & Lichbach, M. I. “To the Internet, from the Internet: Comparative Media Coverage of Transnational Protests.” *Mobilization*, 8:3 (2003): 249–272.

²⁶² Esra Ercan Bilgiç and Zehra Kafkaslı, Gencim, Özgürlükçüyüm, Ne İstiyorum: #direngeziparkı Anketi Sonuç Raporu, (İstanbul Bilgi Üniversitesi Yayınları, 2013) accessed October 20, 2010. <http://www.bilgiyay.com/Content/files/DIRENGEZI.pdf>

²⁶³ Papadimitriou, Alex et al., “Deliverable 2.2: Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations”, *COSMIC*, 2013

²⁶⁴ Mercea, D. 2011. “Digital Prefigurative Participation: The Entwinement of Online Communication and Offline Participation in Protest Events.” *New Media & Society* 14 (1) (December 6): 153–169. Jeffrey S. Juris, “Networked social movements: global movements for global justice,” in *The Network Society: A Cross-cultural Perspective*, ed. Manuel Castells, 347.

²⁶⁵ Castells, Manuel, *Networks of Outrage and Hope*, Polity Press, Cambridge, 2012. check

²⁶⁶ Melissa Wall and Sahar El Zahed, “I’ll Be Waiting for You Guys’: A YouTube Call to Action in the Egyptian Revolution,” *International Journal of Communication* 5 (2011):1333–1343.

²⁶⁷ Manuel Castells, 2012, p.59.

Figure 5. The dissemination of images of the “Blue Bra Girl” via social media was among the catalysts that mobilised the public in Egypt

Similarly, during the Euromaidan protests in Ukraine, images showing police brutality were circulated in social media, which in turn, acted as a catalyst for more people going out into the streets. According to a survey conducted during the Euromaidan protests, majority of protestors (70%) said that the police beating of the protesters on November 30, 2013 was one of the main reasons for joining the protests.²⁶⁸

At this point, it is important to underline the symbiotic nature of use of social media and mass media for connecting with the wider public. As Bennett and Segerberg argue, while online social networks are important, activists need to be visible in mass media to reach and resonate with the masses.²⁶⁹ The mutual relationship between the activists and mass media can be seen in the case of New York Times full-page ad placed by Gezi Park supporters. Turkish activists used social media to crowdfund the fee necessary to place a print advertisement entitled “What’s happening in Turkey” that listed with demands from Turkish Government, such as “end to police brutality” and “free media”.

Especially in countries where illiteracy is relatively high and Internet penetration is low, television continues to be the only source of media for the public. In this context, Al Jazeera’s coverage of the protests in Egypt, underline how the intertwined relationship between mass media with social networks may help disseminate ideas. Al Jazeera, extensively used the voice of the activists in their broadcasts by including the self-produced videos documenting protests, tweets and Facebook posts.²⁷⁰ This allowed activists to be heard by the Arabic public and other international community. Indeed, even, after the international media lost their interest, Aljazeera continued broadcasting from Egypt and to be the link bridging the protesters to communities.²⁷¹

In addition to helping the mobilisation of protestors in a specific geographical location, SNSs also facilitate the exchange of information (and inspiration) between geographically distant

²⁶⁸ “Maidan-2013” Iko Kucheriv Democratic Initiatives Foundation and the Kyiv International Institute of, accessed on N20 Sociology <http://dif.org.ua/en/events/gvkrllgkaeths.htm>

²⁶⁹ Bennett, W. Lance, and Alexandra Segerberg, “Digital Media and the Personalization of Collective Action,” *Information, Communication & Society*, 14:6 (2011): 775.

²⁷⁰ Nehad Ismail, “Arab Revolution, Social Media Hype and Al Jazeera”, *Huffington Post*, December 12, 2011, accessed October 20, 2014 http://www.huffingtonpost.com/nehad-ismail/arab-revolution-social-me_b_1032505.html

²⁷¹ Campbell, Heidi A. and Diana Hawk, “Al Jazeera’s Framing of Social Media During the Arab Spring,” *CyberOrient*, 6:1 (2012), accessed October 20, 2010.

movements; helping them build ties, collaborate, and expand their reach.²⁷² As Tarrow explains, the transnational dimension of social movements is “rooted in domestic social networks and connected to one another more than episodically through common ways of seeing the world, or through informal or organisational ties.”²⁷³

The role social media played in the interaction between 15M in Spain and Indignant Citizens Movement in Greece in 2011 is a case in point that illustrates the increasingly transnational nature of the connections between social movements that share similar goals and concerns. Namely, before the protests both Spain and Greece faced severe economic problems. First, Spanish people took out to the streets, protesting the government for failure to cope with the economic crisis. Interestingly, one of the leading slogans used by the Spaniards in Puerta del Sol was “Shh...the Greeks are sleeping” referring to their not protesting as the Spaniards were doing at the time.²⁷⁴ The slogan went viral, diffused through social media. Greek protesters used social network sites such as Facebook (a page called “Indignants at Syntagma”).²⁷⁵ On May 25th, 30.000 people met outside the Greek Parliament, with banners reading “We’ve awakened! What time is it? Time for them to leave!”.²⁷⁶ Also important to note is that activists on both side established live connections via online video services and social network sites. The intense use of social media during the organisation of the protests resulted in the movement being called by some as “May of Facebook.”²⁷⁷

Figure 6. Greek activist carrying banner saying “the Greeks are sleeping”

3.3.2 Social media, individuals and organisation of activist networks

²⁷² Garrett, R. K. 2006, “Protest in an information society. A review of the Literature on Social Movements and New ICTs,” *Information, Communication & Society*, 9:2(2006):202–224.

²⁷³ Tarrow, Sidney, *Power in Movement: Social Movements and Contentious Politics* (Cambridge University Press, 1998) 184.

²⁷⁴ Bennett, “Logic of Connective Action”

²⁷⁵ Pekka Himanen, “Crisis, Identity, and the Welfare State,” in *Aftermath: The Cultures in Economic Crisis*, ed. Manuel Castells, João Caração, Gustavo Cardoso, (Oxford University Press, 2012), 154-174.

²⁷⁶ “Estamos despiertos! – We are awake!,” *Streets of Athens*, May 26, 2011, accessed October 20, 2014 <http://stamatisgr.wordpress.com/2011/05/26/estamos-despiertos-we-are-awake/>

²⁷⁷ Pekka Himanen, “Crisis, Identity”

In addition to bringing about changes in how social activists can disseminate/access information and organize, social media and the logic of social networking also have had an impact on the organisational logic of social activist networks.

First, at the most basic level, the open structure of activist networks can potentially enable every individual to induce a movement. Take for example Voter March, an organisation that was founded by four individuals “who wanted to express their opposition to the irregularities and egregious conduct of Election 2000 and the direction in which an illegitimate administration was taking the country.”²⁷⁸ The movement utilised the Internet, via blogs and microblogs to organise and recruit members, currently boasting an online community of about 10,000 members.

Second, this ability of the individual to induce networks also brings about a change in the types of individuals involved in social movements. In the specific case of 15M protests, for example, Anduiza observes that social networks helped engage individuals who are not members of political parties and who are less institutionally embedded.²⁷⁹

Third, as observed by Juris, the modus operandi of social media, namely the “networking logic”, which is characterised by decentralised and horizontal forms of communication, have also contributed to a change in the organisational structure of activist networks.²⁸⁰ An important dimension of this change concerns the decision-making mechanisms increasingly being utilised in contemporary activist networks. Namely, various movements, including the 15M movement, described above, strived to challenge the assumptions of representative democracy and top-down methods of organising by trying to include all members in decision-making processes. This tendency was also evident in the Occupy Wall Street Movement, which aimed to adopt decision-making models based on principles of direct democracy. One way that this was achieved was through use of assemblies for making decisions based on consent or modified consent (such as 90% of the consent).

It has been argued that an important consequence of this horizontal approach is that decision making may often become very taxing, often lasting for very long and many times not leading to concrete decisions. Indeed, it has been suggested that this difficulty in making decisions was key in exposing the Occupy Wall Street Movement’s weakness as a movement that could not offer concrete policy proposals.²⁸¹ Yet, the network logic that the Occupy Wall Street Movement adopted arguably also meant that the movement, by design, refrained from coming up with such policy proposals. For example, according to one of the organizers of Occupy Wall Street Movement, deciding on concrete policy proposals, which would potentially mean the exclusion of some opinions, would jeopardise one of the main premises of the Occupy Wall Street Movement as a network that is supposed to represent the 99% of the population.²⁸²

²⁷⁸ “About Voter March”, n.d. <http://votermarch.blogspot.com/p/about-voter-march.html>

²⁷⁹ Eva Anduiza, Camilo Cristancho, and José M. Sabucedo, “Mobilization through Online Social Networks: The Political Protest of the Indignados in Spain,” *Information, Communication & Society* 17, no. 6 (2014): 750–64.

²⁸⁰ Jeffrey Scott Juris, “The Networked Social Movements: Global Movements for Global Justice,” in *The Network Society: A Cross-Cultural Perspective*, ed. Manuel Castells, (Edward Elgar Publications, 2005), 341-361.

²⁸¹ Frank, Thomas. 2012. “To the Precinct Station: How Theory Met Practice and Drove It Absolutely Crazy.” Baffler21 (November). http://www.thebaffler.com/past/to_the_precinct_station

²⁸² Abigail Bellows, “Mind the Gap: Connecting the Movement to the Moderates in India and the United States Bellows,” *Abigail. Kennedy School Review*, 12 (2012).

3.4 CONCLUSION

This chapter has sought to explore some of the privacy, security and activism related challenges that those using new media applications, including social media, to contribute to crisis management should consider and take measures to respond to. Building on from Chapter 2 of this report, partners identified a series of privacy related challenges including policy, informed consent, transparency, anonymity etc. that stakeholders should be aware of, understand and accordingly, implement measures and policies to ensure that the sufficient steps are taken to meet data protection regulations for the sharing, collection and re-use of data for secondary purposes. Partners also discussed the various privacy issues related to the impact of data collection on surveillance, as well as opportunities relating to counter-surveillance, and challenges associated with lateral surveillance that may stem from the growing use of social media in society. Subsequently, partners discussed the various challenges surrounding the protection of information as well as the potential impact of the use of new media technologies on citizens' safety. Finally, the opportunities for social activism for mobilisation, transnational communication and organisation of activist networks were discussed drawing on recent social movements such as Occupy Wall Street, the Arab Spring, 15-M in Spain, protests in Greece, Euromaidan protests in Ukraine, and Gezi Park protests in Turkey. Findings show that social movements dispersed in different geographies can influence and inspire each other and that social networks may also act in ways that influence the modus operandi of activist networks by changing the decision making mechanism and the role individual activists play in contemporary networks.

Overall, this discussion of the various privacy, surveillance and security related challenges to the use of social media in crisis management activities has, where possible, illustrated the need for greater emphasis to be placed on organisations, and in some cases, members of the public, to ensure that they take measures to sufficiently protect those with whom they are interacting, for they may be affected by the actions of others. Thus, as also argued by Büscher et al., there is a growing need to consider how we can go beyond discussing these challenges to more empirical based investigations of how these challenges are being met in reality. By doing so, greater attention can be placed on identifying and sharing good practices with those involved in crisis management activities.

4 CONCLUSION

The present document focused on policies, standards and privacy and security issues in the context of mass utilisation of emerging technologies and information gathering/sharing via social media.

The first part (chapter 2) examined existing policies, standards and opportunities relating to social media and crises. On the policy front, applicable measures taken at EU level cover the areas of privacy, data protection and telecommunications. Current EU legislation concerns the Directive on data protection (1992) and the “Telecommunications Package” and its updates. Policy directions contained in the Digital Agenda point to the need for regulatory intervention on emerging issues such as the openness of the Internet and the freedom of citizens to access and run applications and content.

The partners highlighted the relevance of the reform of the current Data Protection Directive, proposed by the European Commission, and, in particular, its provision for added protection of online data via the “right to oblivion” (Article 17). On the telecommunications side, the implications of the, as yet unsettled, issue of the lack of an EU-wide imposed minimum bandwidth obligation on a Universal Provider were noted as a pending policy issue potentially affecting social network based communication, especially during a crisis.

The question of standardisation in social media was found to affect aspects such as compatibility, interoperability, safety and quality both from the point of view of the industry as well as the consumers. The partners examined standardisation challenges such as the underlying telecommunications technologies, the presentation layer of social media, the data involved and the means of interacting with social media services. For the semantics-rich social media data, representation mechanisms such as Linked Data were identified and commented upon, along with various emerging attempts for describing semantic models, primarily using general ontologies for social media entities and specialised ones for describing concepts of crises. The partners noted here that there has been no systematic research effort to address the common ground of both streams, i.e. semantic interoperability for social media in crisis management.

In addition, examination of the developing and varied landscape of tools for interacting with social media services revealed the complex interplay between market leaders and their competitors and correspondingly between proprietary and open standards. To illustrate the point, examples of the standardisation effort at two different international organisations, with differing missions were presented, in which they both, through the need to serve their purpose, recognised the necessity for standardisation in social media and work actively towards its achievement.

Chapter three sought to identify and discuss some of the privacy security and citizen organisation related challenges that those utilising new media applications to contribute to crisis management should consider, and subsequently, take measures to respond to. Building on from chapter 2, partners identified EU policies on data protection that stakeholders should be aware of, understand and accordingly, implement measures and policies to ensure that the sufficient steps are taken to meet data protection regulations for the sharing, collection and re-use of data for secondary purposes. Partners discussed the various related issues for stakeholders to consider, including: informed consent; transparency; proportionality and legitimate purpose; anonymity and the impact of increased surveillance. Finally, partners

discussed the various challenges surrounding the protection of information as well as the potential impact of the use of new media technologies on citizens' safety. The partners aimed to demonstrate that although there are a number of challenges to be considered, there are viable approaches to meeting these challenges. By engaging with these challenges, stakeholders can continue to build trusting relationships, which will enable social media to become part of crisis management. Overall, this discussion of the various privacy and security related challenges to the use of social media in crisis management activities has, where possible, illustrated the need for greater emphasis to be placed on organisations, and in some cases, members of the public, to ensure that they take measures to sufficiently protect those with whom they are interacting, for they may be affected by the actions of others.

Finally, the opportunities for social activism for mobilisation, transnational communication and organisation of activist networks were discussed drawing on recent social movements such as Occupy Wall Street, the Arab Spring, 15-M in Spain, protests in Greece, Euromaidan protests in Ukraine, and Gezi Park protests in Turkey. Findings show that social movements dispersed in different geographies can influence and inspire each other and that social networks may also act in ways that influence the modus operandi of activist networks by changing the decision-making mechanism and the role individual activists play in contemporary networks.